

Yannick Mayer

Fluid dynamical and reaction engineering characterization of a reaction mixing pump

Master thesis

Published: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Erik von Harbou

Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität
Fachbereich für Maschinenbau und Verfahrenstechnik

Master thesis

Fluid dynamical and reaction engineering characterization of a reaction mixing pump

submitted to

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Erik von Harbou

Laboratory of Reaction and Fluid Process Engineering

supervised by:

Erik von Harbou (scientific)

erik.vonharbou@rptu.de

Christian Weibel (administrative)

christian.weibel@rptu.de

written by:

Yannick Mayer, Matr.-Nr.: 400915

ymayer@rptu.de

Kaiserslautern, 5th of May 2023

Abstract

Multiple fluid phases frequently occur in many processes utilized in the chemical industry. To achieve good mass and heat transfer between the individual phases, a large interfacial area is required. Therefore stirred tank reactors, characterized by their good mixing properties, are often used. Reaction mixing pumps (RMP) represent a promising alternative to stirred tank reactors, as they combine mixing and transportation of the reaction media, thus leading to process intensification. This type of pumps has been less researched so far. Hence the aim of this work is to investigate fluid dynamical and reaction engineering properties of a RMP that can convey up to 400 L h^{-1} , in order to estimate the behaviour of an RMP when used as a reactor. First, pump characteristic curves were recorded for this purpose. A parameter-based fluid dynamic model developed by Dr.-Ing. Oliver Bey (BASF SE), which predicts the pump characteristic curves, was fitted to the experimental data. The adaption of Bey's model to experimental data showed that the fluid dynamic model is capable of describing the pump characteristic curves with high accuracy for a given impeller speed and flow rate. The parameters obtained by fitting Bey's model to the experimental data were used to determine internal flow rates of the RMP. The internal flow rates were utilized in a compartment model to predict the residence time behaviour of the RMP, which is intended to derive statements about the RMP as a reactor, from fluid dynamical characteristics alone. To verify these predictions, the residence time behaviour of the reaction mixing pump was examined by conducting tracer experiments. It could be shown, that the model can predict the residence time behavior well at low flow rates, while bigger deviations occurred at higher flow rates. Furthermore, the compartment model was used to simulate a reaction inside the RMP. Comparatively, the reaction was also simulated in an ideal stirred tank reactor. The simulation showed that minor deviations between RMP and CSTR occur at low flow rate while the differences between the two reactor types increases with higher flow rates.

Kurzfassung

Häufig treten bei vielen in der chemischen Industrie genutzten Prozessen mehrere fluide Phasen auf. Um einen guten Stoff- und Wärmetransport zwischen den einzelnen Phasen zu gewährleisten, wird eine große Phasengrenzfläche benötigt. Daher werden häufig Rührkesselreaktoren verwendet, da in diesen Reaktoren eine hohe Dispersion und somit große Phasengrenzflächen erreicht werden. Eine vielversprechende Alternative zu den Rührkesselreaktoren stellen dabei Reaktionsmischpumpen (RMP) dar, da sie das gleichzeitige Mischen und Transportieren des Reaktionsmediums ermöglichen, was zu einer Prozessintensivierung führt. Diese Art von Pumpen sind bisher wenig erforscht. Ziel dieser Arbeit ist deshalb die fluiddynamische und reaktionstechnische Charakterisierung einer RMP, die bis zu 400 L h^{-1} fördern kann, um das Verhalten der RMP als Reaktor besser abschätzen zu können. Zunächst wurden dazu Pumpenkennlinien aufgenommen. Ein von Dr.-Ing. Oliver Bey (BASF SE) entwickeltes parameterbasiertes fluiddynamisches Modell, das die Pumpenkennlinien beschreibt wurde dann an die experimentellen Pumpenkennlinien angepasst. Dabei zeigte sich, dass das Modell in der Lage ist, die Pumpenkennlinien bei gegebener Laufraddrehzahl und Volumenstrom mit hoher Genauigkeit abzubilden. Die Parameter, die durch die Anpassung von Beys Modell an die experimentellen Daten erhalten wurden, konnten dann verwendet werden, um interne Strömungen innerhalb der RMP zu bestimmen. Die so bestimmten Ströme wurden dann in einem Compartment-Modell verwendet, um das Verweilzeitverhalten der RMP vorherzusagen und so allein aus den Pumpenkennlinien Aussagen über das Verhalten der RMP als Reaktor treffen zu können. Um diese Vorhersagen zu überprüfen, wurde zusätzlich das Verweilzeitverhalten der Reaktionsmischpumpe mittels Tracer-Versuchen untersucht. Dabei zeigte sich, dass das Modell besonders bei niedrigen Volumenströmen das Verweilzeitverhalten gut vorhersagen kann, während bei größeren Volumenströmen eine höhere Abweichung zwischen Modell und experimentellen Daten beobachtet werden konnte. Weiterhin wurde das Compartment-Modell genutzt, um eine Reaktion in der RMP zu simulieren. Vergleichend dazu wurde die Reaktion auch bei gleichen Betriebsbedingungen in einem idealen Rührkessel simuliert. Die Simulation zeigte das bei hohen Volumenströmen große Unterschiede zwischen den beiden Reaktortypen (RMP vs. CSTR) auftreten, während bei niedrigen Volumenströmen kleinere Abweichungen zu beobachten sind.

Contents

Abstract	I
Kurzfassung	II
Nomenclature	V
1. Introduction	1
2. Theoretical Background	3
2.1. Reaction mixing pumps	3
2.1.1. Assembly of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps	3
2.1.2. Internal fluid dynamics of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps	3
2.2. Fluid dynamic model of the RMP	5
2.3. Reactor model of the RMP	7
3. Materials and Methods	9
3.1. Experimental set up	9
3.2. Experimental procedure	11
3.2.1. Measuring of the pump characteristic curves	11
3.2.2. Measuring of the residence time	12
3.3. Parameter estimation and simulation	13
3.3.1. Implementation of the model equations	13
3.3.2. Adapting the fluid dynamic model to experimental pump characteristic curves	13
3.3.3. Residence time behaviour	14
3.3.4. Determination of residence time distribution by deconvolution	15
3.4. Simulative study of the reaction behaviour of the RMP	16
4. Results and Discussion	17
4.1. Fluid dynamical investigation	17
4.1.1. Estimation of the parameters used in the fluid dynamic model	17
4.1.2. Parametrical sensitivity of the fluid dynamic model	19
4.1.3. Efficiency of the RMP	20
4.1.4. Internal flow characteristics of the pump	22
4.2. Characterization of the RMP as a reactor	25
4.2.1. Comparison between predicted and experimental residence time behaviour	25
4.2.2. Parametrical sensitivity of the compartment model	28
4.2.3. Reconstructing the residence time distribution by deconvolution	30
4.2.4. Simulation of the reactive behaviour of the RMP	32

5. Conclusion	38
6. Outlook	40
Bibliography	43
A. Appendix	44
A.1. Supplementary theoretical background	44
A.1.1. Pumps	44
A.1.2. Efficiency of Pumps	45
A.1.3. Chemical reactions	45
A.1.4. Derivation of balance equations for chemical reactors	47
A.1.5. Conservation laws	48
A.1.6. Ideal reactor models	49
A.2. Further information on the experimental set up	51
A.2.1. List of the equipment used	51
A.2.2. Drawing of the RMP and geometrical properties	52
A.2.3. Assembly and calibration of the photosensors	53
A.3. Alternative approaches to determine the tracer concentration	55
A.4. Error estimation	59
A.4.1. Pump characteristic curves	59
A.5. Calculation of the trust region for the ζ -parameters	59
A.6. Number of circulations	61
A.7. Convolution	62
A.8. Flow fractions inside the RMP	64
A.9. Additional results from the simulative study	67
Eidesstattliche Erklärung	72

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

Symbol	Meaning
AC	alternating current
AoS	amount of substance
CSTR	continous stirred tank reaktor
cf.	confer
DFFT	discrete fast fourier transform
iDFFT	inverse discrete fast fourier transform
ODE	ordinary differential equation
PDE	partial differential equation
PFR	plug flow reactor
PMMA	Poly(methyl methacrylate)
Rad	radiant
RPTU	Rheinland Pfälzische Technische Universität
STR	stirred tank reactor
s.t.	subject to

Symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
A	area	m^2
B	number of impeller blades	m^2
C	number of circulations	1
c	concentration	kg L^{-1}
f	rotational speed	s^{-1}
g	weighing factor	1
h	height	m
K	number of vessels	1
k	reaction rate constant	$\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
l	length	m
\dot{m}	mass flow rate	kg min^{-1}
N	number of components	1
n	amount of substance	mol
\dot{n}	molar flow rate	mol min^{-1}
P	power	W
p	pressure	bar

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
R	number of reactions	1
r	radius	m
rr	reaction rate	$\text{mol L}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
S	selectivity	1
s	slope	N m s
T	torque	N m
t	time	s
u	speed	m s^{-1}
V	volume	m^3
\dot{V}	flow rate	L min^{-1}
X	conversion	1
Y	yield	1
z	spatial coordinate	m
γ	smoothing factor	1
ϵ	roughness	m
ζ	loss coefficients	1
η	efficiency	1
μ	dynamic viscosity	Pa s
ν	stoichiometric number	1
ρ	density	kg L^{-1}
$\bar{\tau}$	space time	s
φ	angle	$^\circ$
ω	angular Speed	Rad s^{-1}

Indices

Symbol	Meaning
A	substance A
B	substance B
bc	breaker channel
bl	blade
C	substance C
CSTR	continous stirred tank reaktor
cen	center of mass
circ	circulation
comp	compartment
conj	conjugate
conv	convolution
cur	curvature
D	substance D
E	effective

Index	Meaning
exp	experimental
i	inner
imp	impeller
in	inlet
j	control variable
k	control variable
l	control variable
o	outer
opt	optimum
out	outlet
S	shaft
sc	side channel
0	idle

List of Figures

2.1. Schematic assembly of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps	3
2.2. Internal circulation	4
2.3. 2D-projection of the spiral-shaped motion	4
2.4. Compartment model of the RMP	7
3.1. Flowsheet of the experimental set up	9
3.2. Assembly of RMP	10
3.3. Scheme for the calculation of $c_{\text{out}}(t - \tau_{PS2})$	14
4.1. Pressure increase of the pump as a function of the flow rate for different rotational speeds	17
4.2. Sensitivity of the fluid dynamic model to the different ζ -parameters used	19
4.3. Efficiency of the RMP for different rotational speeds	21
4.4. Pump characteristic curves with different backmixing regions	24
4.5. Measured and predicted residence time behaviour at different operating points	26
4.6. Flow from the stagnant zone inside the RMP	28
4.7. Sensitivity of the compartment model to the different ζ -parameters	29
4.8. Residence time distribution obtained by deconvolution	31
4.9. Relative conversion for the simulated reaction network	33
4.10. Relative sensitivity for the simulated reaction network	35
4.11. Relative yield for the simulated reaction network	36
A.1. Characteristic map of different pump types	44
A.2. Pump characteristic curves and an exemplary system characteristic curve	45
A.3. Differential element	47
A.4. Drawing of the RMP	52
A.5. Assembly of photosensor	53
A.6. Control unit of the photosensor	53
A.7. Sensitivity of the photosensor for different LED settings	54
A.8. Calibration of the photosensor	55
A.9. Picture of impeller taken with high speed cam	56
A.10. Grey value for different tracer concentrations	56
A.11. Images of pipe segment at different tracer concentrations	57
A.12. RGB values at different tracer concentrations.	58
A.13. Deconvolution depending on the smoothing factor	63
A.14. Investigated operating points of the simulative study	68
A.15. Relative conversion (Additional simulation results)	69
A.16. Relative selectivity (Additional simulation results)	70
A.17. Relative yield (Additional simulation results)	71

List of Tables

4.1. Comparison of the values of the ζ -parameters obtained in this work to [3]	18
4.2. Internal volume flow fractions inside the RMP	22
A.2. Investigated operating points for simulative study	67

1. Introduction

In many reactions used in industrial processes multiple fluid phases occur. In general the desired reaction takes only place in one of those phases, thus a sufficient mass- and heat transfer must be provided [1]. The efficiency of the transport is limited among other things by the size of the interfacial area. Therefore it is desired to maximize the area between the single phases.

For this reason stirred tank reactors (STR) are often used in industrial processes, because they are characterized by their good mixing properties leading to a high dispersion. However this high dispersion is achieved by a high energy input into the vessel.

Reaction mixing pumps (RMP) represent an alternative to stirred tank reactors since they combine mixing and transportation of the reaction media leading to a process intensification.

In order to be able to use RMPs as reactors in future applications, they must first be investigated with regard to their reaction engineering properties. These investigations should make it possible to estimate the behaviour of the RMP as a reactor and thus to predict yield and selectivity for an arbitrary reaction network. In principle, these key figures can be predicted from residence time measurements. However, residence time measurements are costly and are usually not performed by the pump manufacturer. This means that in the context of process development, there is no sufficient data basis on which to select and dimension a suitable RMP. Therefore, the aim of this work is to verify whether the reaction engineering behavior of the RMP can be predicted via a compartment model derived in [2, 3]. A drawback of compartment models is that internal flow rates and volumes are usually unknown. For this reason, this work uses an approach in which the internal flow rates are derived from a fluid dynamic model. This parameter-based model was developed by O. Bey and is able to describe the pump characteristic curves. The parameters used describe friction losses within the pump. Pump characteristic curves are given by the manufacturer and are therefore available for the design and dimensioning of the pump. If no pump characteristic curves are given by the manufacturer, they can be measured without large experimental expenditure. By fitting the fluid dynamic model to pump characteristic curves of the RMP, the parameters can be determined and the internal flow rates of the RMP can be calculated.

Eberweiser [3] already tested this approach for a small RMP ($\dot{V}_{\max} = 80 \text{ L h}^{-1}$) (in the following, this pump will be referred to as RMP80). It was shown that the fluid dynamic model can be adapted very well to experimental pump characteristic curves of the RMP80. Furthermore, it was shown in [3] by comparison with residence time measurements that the residence time behaviour can be predicted very accurately via the compartment model proposed in [2, 3], in which the internal flow rates, determined from the fluid dynamic model, were used. However, it was also shown in [3] that the residence time behavior can be predicted with equal accuracy by modeling the RMP as an ideal CSTR, which could be due to the fact, that the differences between the two reactor models were lower than the measurement uncertainty.

For this reason, the methodological procedure from [3] was adapted for a larger RMP ($\dot{V}_{\max} = 400 \text{ L h}^{-1}$) in the scope of this thesis (this RMP will be referred to as RMP400 in the following). For this purpose, the fluid dynamic behavior was characterized by determining pump characteristic curves at different impeller speeds. To determine the parameters and ultimately the internal flow rates from Bey's approach, the model was fitted to experimental data. For the sake of completeness, this paper also proposes a method that could allow the estimation of the pump efficiency without the need for complex torque measurements.

To verify whether the proposed compartment model can predict the residence time behaviour and thus is a suitable candidate for a reactor model of the RMP, tracer experiments were performed to determine the residence time. In order to compare the behavior of the RMP for reactive systems with the behavior of an ideal CSTR, the conversion, selectivity, and yield for a simple reaction network were investigated in simulation studies. In these studies, the RMP was depicted using the compartment model. A main reaction with a 2nd order side reaction was chosen as the reaction system, since for such reaction networks the internal backmixing has a direct influence on the reactions outcome.

The experimental and simulative investigations showed that the reactor behaviour of the larger RMP400, in contrast to the RMP80, differs in some cases from that of an ideal CSTR. The results of this work suggest that the desired mixing behavior can be determined by the choice of the operating point of the pump, which makes them interesting and versatile apparatuses from a reaction engineering point of view.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Reaction mixing pumps

The investigated reaction mixing pump is a peripheral pump which is a special type of side channel pumps. Side channel pumps are characterized by their star-shaped impeller [4]. Side channel pumps lie between positive displacement and classic centrifugal pumps in terms of head and flow rate in the characteristic curve and thus represent a link between these two pump types [4]. A short review on pumps in general can be found in the appendix (cf. Subsec. A.1.1).

2.1.1. Assembly of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps

Side channel and peripheral pumps represent a special type of flow pumps. The name is derived from the fact, that the pumps interior is divided into different sections, respectively an impeller channel and a side channel. Inlet and outlet of the pump are separated by a breaker channel.

Fig. 2.1.: Schematic assembly of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps. A) front view of the impeller with different sections, B) side view of a side channel pump and C) side view of a peripheral pump. The drawing indicates the axial interface of the different channels.

Side channel and peripheral pumps differ in the design of their star-shaped impeller and by the fact that the peripheral pump has two side channels connected in parallel. The axial interfaces of the different channels are indicated in Fig. 2.1.

2.1.2. Internal fluid dynamics of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps

A theory to describe the internal fluid dynamics of side channel pumps and peripheral pumps is the circulation theory which is described by Grabow and Suong [5]:

A fluid element inside the impeller channel is pressed towards the impeller tips due to centrifugal forces caused by the impellers rotation. Following fluid then displaces the fluid element into

the side channel, where it follows the outer geometry of the side channel [3]. Finally, the fluid element is pushed back into the impeller channel, hence completing a full rotation. Since the impeller rotates in axial direction, the superposition of axial and radial movement leads to a spiral shaped motion of the fluid element (cf. Fig. 2.2), thus there is always an exchange of mass \dot{m}_{circ} between side- and impeller channel.

Fig. 2.2.: Circulation between side- and impeller channel. The 2D-projection of the 3D-movement is indicated by the dashed line. For a better overview, the impeller blades are not shown in this figure. The impeller rotates in x direction as indicated by \dot{V}_{imp} .

Due to the rotation, the direction in which the fluid element moves always changes and therefore is accompanied by an exchange of momentum between adjacent fluid elements. This exchange of momentum summed up over the whole pump leads to an increase of pressure inside the pump.

According to Muschelknautz [6], the circular part of the spiral shaped motion (the 2D-projection on the yz-plane in Fig. 2.2) only depends on geometric properties of the pump [6].

Fig. 2.3.: 2D-projection of the spiral-shaped motion on the yz-plane inside a side channel pump. Own illustration according to [6].

Accordingly, the circulation radii $r_{\text{circ}}, r_{\text{circ},1}, r_{\text{circ},2}$ visualized in Fig. 2.3 can be described by the following equations [6]:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{\text{circ}} &= \frac{r_{\text{imp},i} + r_{\text{imp},o}}{2} + \frac{d_{\text{sc}}}{6} \\ r_{\text{circ},1} &= \frac{r_{\text{imp},i} + r_{\text{imp},o}}{2} - \frac{d_{\text{sc}}}{6} \\ r_{\text{circ},2} &= \frac{r_{\text{imp},i} + r_{\text{imp},o}}{2} + \frac{2d_{\text{sc}}}{6} \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

The diameter d_{sc} is the diameter of a hemisphere, whose projection area equals the side channel area A_{sc} . In the case of the peripheral pump only half of the side channel area is taken into account, since the method proposed by Muschelknautz [6] only refers to one side channel.

2.2. Fluid dynamic model of the RMP

The model developed by O. Bey utilizes the circulation theory, and is based on the exchange of mass and momentum between the side channel and impeller channel of the pump. The model consists of three equations, respectively:

- A coupled mass and angular momentum balance:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{circ}} \cdot (\omega_{\text{imp}} \cdot r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - u_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{circ},1}) = \left(\Delta p \cdot r_{\text{circ}} + \zeta_{\text{sc}} \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot u_{\text{sc}}^{*2} \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \right) \cdot \frac{A_{\text{sc}}^*}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

- The mass exchange due to the circulation derived from a force balance along the radial axis:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{circ}}(u_{\text{sc}}^*, \omega_{\text{imp}}, \zeta_{\text{circ}}) = \rho \cdot A_{\text{circ, cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2 \right) \cdot \left(\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \left(\frac{u_{\text{sc}}^*}{r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*} \right)^2 \right)} \quad (2.3)$$

- and a term describing the side-channel speed u_{sc}^* derived from a continuity equation:

$$u_{\text{sc}}^*(\dot{V}_{\text{in}}, \Delta p, \zeta_{\text{bc}}) = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}}{A_{\text{sc}}^*} + \frac{A_{\text{bc}}}{A_{\text{sc}}^*} \cdot \zeta_{\text{bc}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot \Delta p}{\rho}} \quad (2.4)$$

The asterisk in Eq. (2.2 - 2.4) indicates that at these values the breaker channel is considered part of the respective channel.

$\zeta_{\text{sc}}, \zeta_{\text{circ}}$ and ζ_{bc} represent friction loss coefficients and are later utilized to calculate the internal flow rates \dot{V}_{sc}^* and \dot{V}_{circ} . A detailed and good derivation of Eq. (2.2 - 2.4) can be found in [3].

Rearranging of Eq. (2.2) and inserting the definitions derived by Eq. (2.3) and (2.4) leads to the following equation:

$$F(\dot{V}_{\text{in}}, \omega_{\text{imp}}, \Delta p, \zeta) = \left(\Delta p \cdot r_{\text{circ}} + \zeta_{\text{sc}} \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot (u_{\text{sc}}^*(\dot{V}_{\text{in}}, \Delta p, \zeta_{\text{bc}}))^2 \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \right) \cdot \frac{A_{\text{sc}}^*}{2} - \dot{m}_{\text{circ}}(u_{\text{sc}}^*(\dot{V}_{\text{in}}, \Delta p, \zeta_{\text{bc}}), \omega_{\text{imp}}, \zeta_{\text{circ}}) \cdot \left(\omega_{\text{imp}} \cdot r_{\text{circ}, 2}^2 - u_{\text{sc}}^*(\dot{V}_{\text{in}}, \Delta p, \zeta_{\text{bc}}) \cdot r_{\text{circ}, 1} \right) \quad (2.5)$$

The fluid dynamic model can also be used to derive analytical equations via which internal volume flow ratios can be calculated from the geometry, the ζ -parameters and the operating point. This approach was first proposed by Eberweiser [3] and is continued in this work. A derivation of the respective equations can be found in the appendix (cf. Sec. A.8).

To describe the operating point of the pump first a new dimensionless parameter ξ is introduced which describes the ratio of two angular speeds:

$$\xi_{k,j} = \frac{\omega_k}{\omega_j} \quad (2.6)$$

With ω_j describing the angular speed in the respective channel j, k of the pump.

The ratio of the flow rate in the impeller channel \dot{V}_{imp} versus the circulation flow rate \dot{V}_{circ} and thus the circulation ratio of the impeller channel can be described by the following equation:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}, m} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}, \text{opt}} \cdot \sqrt{r_{\text{circ}, 2}^2 - r_{\text{circ}, 1}^2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \xi_{\text{sc}, \text{imp}}^2}} \quad (2.7)$$

and respectively the ratio of the side channel flow rate \dot{V}_{sc}^* versus the circulation flow rate \dot{V}_{circ} . Hence the circulation ratio of the side channel can be calculated by the following equation:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc}, m}^*}{2 \cdot A_{\text{circ}, m} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}, \text{opt}} \cdot \sqrt{r_{\text{circ}, 2}^2 - r_{\text{circ}, 1}^2}} \cdot \frac{\xi_{\text{sc}, \text{imp}}}{\sqrt{1 - \xi_{\text{sc}, \text{imp}}^2}} \quad (2.8)$$

$\xi_{\text{sc}, \text{imp}} < 1$ can always be assumed since a fluid element leaving the impeller channel is always slowed down in the side channel due to friction losses, but it must be taken into account that \dot{V}_{sc}^* can become bigger than \dot{V}_{imp} since $V_{\text{sc}}^* > V_{\text{imp}}$.

Another factor that significantly influences the mixing behavior within the pump, is the ratio of the recycled flow rate and the actual conveyed flow rate, the recycle ratio:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}} + V_{\text{bc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{bc,imp}}}{\frac{360}{\varphi_{\text{sc}}} \cdot V_{\text{sc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{sc,imp}} + V_{\text{bc}} \cdot (\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} - \xi_{\text{bc,imp}})} \quad (2.9)$$

$\xi_{\text{bc,imp}} < 1$ can also be assumed due to friction losses. With $V_{\text{bc}} \ll V_{\text{imp}}$, the following simplification can be made:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{\frac{360}{\varphi_{\text{sc}}} \cdot V_{\text{sc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{sc,imp}}} \quad (2.10)$$

2.3. Reactor model of the RMP

One approach to describe the RMP as a reactor is by a compartment model. As the name suggests the volume of the RMP is divided into smaller compartments. Each of these compartments is treated like an ideal CSTR (Assumptions: isothermic, constant density):

$$\frac{dc_{\text{out},j}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{V}_k}{V_j} \cdot (c_{\text{in}} - c_{\text{out}}) + \underline{\underline{v}} \cdot rr \quad (2.11)$$

With j being the respective compartment and k the stream that flows into the compartment.

A peripheral pump, and therefore also the investigated RMP consists of two side channel pumps connected in parallel (cf. Fig. 3.2). This symmetry can be used in the compartment model, which means that only one side channel needs to be considered. However, it must be taken into account that the flow rates and the volumes must be halved. The only exception to this is the circulation flow rate \dot{V}_{circ} . The impeller, side and breaker channels are then divided further into smaller vessels. Previous considerations resulted in the following compartment model of the RMP [2, 3], which is based on the assembly of the pump:

Fig. 2.4.: Compartment model of the RMP to predict the behaviour of the RMP as a reactor.

The parameters used in the compartment model can be taken from Bey's fluid dynamic model:

- \dot{V}_{sc}^* by multiplying Eq. (2.4) with A_{sc}^*
- \dot{V}_{circ} by dividing Eq. (2.3) with ρ

and the pumps geometry, respectively (cf. Subsec. A.2.2).

For the model used the number of compartments K_j , K_k and K_l in the respective channel correspond to the number of the impeller chambers of the RMP. Since there are no impeller chambers in the side channel, the number of side channel compartments is equal to those of the impeller channel.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Experimental set up

Fig. 3.1 shows the flowsheet of the test rig:

Fig. 3.1.: Flowsheet of the experimental set up including all control units. P1 is the pump, FI is a flowmeter, PR is a pressure recorder and ER a voltage recorder.

There are three tanks. One (T3) containing deionized water (hereafter only referred to as water), a second one containing an aqueous solution in which a tracer substance is dissolved (T2) and a third tank (T1), which was only used for calibration purposes and for filling T2. To choose between T2 and T3, a solenoid valve (V6) is used. Downstream is a flowmeter (FI). Afterwards the stream is split into two conduits and is joined again after a short distance, hence dividing the streams into one main stream and a bypass. Via solenoid valves (V7 and V8) the stream can be routed either through the main conduit or the bypass, while in the respective other conduit a defined volume is trapped. The output of V8 is then lead into the first part of the measuring section (cf. left half of Fig. 3.2) consisting of a pressure sensor (PR 2) and a photosensor (PS 1) to measure the concentration of a tracer at the inlet of the RMP (P1). Downstream of the pump is the second part of the measuring section which is constructed mirror-inverted to the first part of the measuring section (cf. right half of Fig. 3.2). First comes a photosensor (PS 2) to measure the concentration of a tracer substance at the outlet of P1 and then a pressure sensor (PR 5) to measure the pressure at the output of P1. A needle valve (V9) is then used to alter the flow

resistance and thus the test rig characteristic curve. A ball valve (V2) which is positioned at the lowest point of the test rig is used to vent the system in the case of trapped air inside the conduits. The pumped medium can then be fed back into T3 or into the drain which can be selected via solenoid valve (V1).

Fig. 3.2.: Assembly of the RMP with pressure and photo sensors. The flow direction is indicated by green arrows.

To control the solenoid valves (C1866022, Festo Beteiligungen GmbH Co. KG, Germany) a valve control unit was used. The control unit was assembled at the workshops of the RPTU.

The used pump (HMI 100, K-Engineering GmbH, Germany) was driven by a frequency converter (VF-S11, ToshibaCorp., Japan), which can vary the frequency of an alternating current (AC) from 0-50 Hz, hence altering the impeller speed.

To make the impeller visible, the metal housing of the pump was substituted by a Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) housing (cf. Fig. 3.2). A high speed camera (Os8S3, Imaging Solutions GmbH, Germany) was placed in front of the pump to record images of the rotating impeller. These images were later used to calculate the actual rotational speed of the impeller.

The data obtained by the sensors PR 2, ER 3, ER 4 and PR 5 was recorded by a data-logger (ALMEMO 2890-9, Ahlborn Mess- und Regelungstechnik GmbH, Germany).

The photo sensors consist of a LED and a phototransistor, which are arranged opposite each other. Between them is the measuring gap through which the pumped fluid flows. The intensity of the incident light emitted by the LED changes the voltage drop of the phototransistor. This voltage drop is then recorded via ER 3 and 4. According to Beer-Lambert's law, the intensity of the transmitted light depends on concentration of the used tracer substance (Brilliant Black, CAS Registry Number: 2519-30-4, Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG, Germany). A higher concentration leads to a lower transmission of the light and vice versa. The brightness of the LED and the sensitivity of the phototransistor can be controlled by the photo sensor control unit. The sensors and the control unit were assembled at the workshops of the RPTU (for further reading on the photo sensors cf. Subsec. A.2.3).

A complete list of the geometric properties of the pump, a technical drawing and a list of the used equipment can be found in the appendix (cf. Subsec. A.2.1 and A.2.2).

3.2. Experimental procedure

The test rig can be operated in two modes. One for measuring pump characteristic curves, and the other for measuring the residence time of the tracer substance inside the RMP.

3.2.1. Measuring of the pump characteristic curves

To measure the pump characteristic curves for a certain impeller speed, water was circulated in the test rig. The flow rate was adjusted by the needle valve (V9). In order to achieve a steady-state operation, after setting the flow rate, the test rig was left to run for at least 5 minutes before starting the measurement. After the 5 minutes had passed, the pressure at the in- and outlet of the pump was recorded every 10 seconds for 5 minutes. The mean of the 31 measurements was calculated and the difference represents the pressure difference between in- and outlet.

The flow rate indicated by FI was noted at ten different times within this 5 minute time frame, the mean of this 10 values represents the flow rate at this certain operating point. The impeller speed was varied between 40 and 100 percent of the maximum rated speed. For each impeller speed, 10-12 different operating points (pairs of a certain pressure difference Δp and flow rate \dot{V}_{in}) were measured.

Although the measuring accuracy of the pressure sensors used is already very high, occurring fluctuations could be reduced by averaging the high amount of measurements. Therefore measurement uncertainty illustrated by error bars is within the range of the symbols that represented the experimental data in the following figures. Hence error bars are not depicted in this work.

The error that occurs due to friction losses in the inlet and outlet sections and due to the difference in height of the pressure sensors is approx. 0.042bar in the worst case scenario (highest flow rate at lowest impeller speed) and can therefore be neglected. When estimating the friction losses occurring between the two pressure sensors, the highest value for the pipe roughness given in the literature was deliberately chosen so that it can be assumed that the actual pressure loss and thus the error is lower than assumed. A more detailed description of the error estimation can be found in Subsec. A.4.1.

3.2.2. Measuring of the residence time

To determine the residence time of the tracer in the pump, a calibration was first carried out in order to be able to infer the respective concentration from the measured voltage. The procedure for this calibration is explained in the appendix (cf. Subsec. A.2.3).

For the measurement of the residence time first V1 and V6 were turned on and the system was flushed with tracer solution from T2 until the voltage measured at the two photosensors remained constant. Then solenoid valves V7 and V8 were turned on, trapping a part of the tracer solution inside the bypass. Afterwards V6 was turned off and the system was flushed with water from T3, again until a constant voltage at the two photosensors was measured. Afterwards the water is circulated by turning V1 off. Since T3 had partially emptied during flushing, the tank was filled up with water.

Then the desired impeller speed was set and the flow rate was adjusted via V9. Again, to reach a steady-state operation, the test rig was left to run for at least 5 minutes. After the 5 minutes had passed, V1 was turned on first, in order to avoid entrainment of the released tracer into T3. As the turning on of V1 caused the flow rate to change slightly, because the liquid was not circulated into T3 but conveyed into the drain, another 30 seconds were waited before starting the measurement. After the 30 seconds had passed, the measurement was started. The voltage at the photosensors as well as the pressure at the in- and outlet of the RMP was recorded every 50 milliseconds. Then the trapped tracer was released by turning V7 and V8 off simultaneously. While the tracer was flushed out by the water from T3, the flow rate indicated by FI was noted. The recording was stopped after the voltage drop of the photosensors reached a constant value. This experiment was conducted for 3 different operation points at 3 different impeller speeds, respectively 40, 60 and 90 Percent of the maximum rated impeller speed, giving a total of nine different operating points investigated. Each experiment was repeated 3 times.

The calibration (cf. Fig. A.8) suggests that the sensitivity of the sensor strongly depends on the tracer concentration, which was also observed by Eberweiser [3]. At low concentrations ($<0.002 \text{ g L}^{-1}$), a large concentration change results in only a small change in voltage, while at larger concentrations a large sensitivity of the sensor can be observed. This low sensitivity at low concentration makes the accuracy of the measurement sensitive to measurement noise. To average out the impact of the measurement noise and therefore achieve a smoothing of the measured voltage curves, each experiment was repeated three times. This averaging allowed the voltage to be determined very accurately and fluctuations only occurred in the range in which a high change in voltage was observed anyway.

The inlet and outlet distances have an effect on the measured residence time. Although the experimental set up kept the distance as small as possible, the volumes of the two conduits (sensor to inlet and outlet to sensor, respectively) summed up corresponds to about 20 % of the volume of the reaction mixing pump and therefore can not be neglected in the reactor model of the RMP.

The evaluation of the residence time measurements showed that the conservation of mass was violated by more than 10 % $\left(\frac{\int c_{in,exp}(t)dt - \int c_{out,exp}(t)dt}{\int c_{in,exp}(t)dt} > 0.1 \right)$ in some of the experiments carried out. These experiments will not be considered further, since the reactor model is based on this conservation of mass and thus a comparison between model and experimental data is not expedient.

3.3. Parameter estimation and simulation

3.3.1. Implementation of the model equations

The implementation of the different mathematical models was realized in the programming language Julia (Version 1.6.3, macOS 13.0, Jeff Bezanson et al., USA) in the programming environment Visual Studio Code (Version 1.76.2, macOS 13.0, Microsoft, USA).

3.3.2. Adapting the fluid dynamic model to experimental pump characteristic curves

Eq. (2.2 - 2.4) were summarized into a function $\underline{F}(\dot{V}_{exp}, \omega_{imp,exp}, \underline{\Delta p}, \underline{\zeta})$, which has the experimental flow rate and rotational speed, the pressure difference and the ζ -parameters as input values (cf. Sec. 2.2). To estimate the ζ -parameters a least square approach was used (cf. Eq. (3.1)). The objective function computes the sum of squared errors between the pressure difference predicted by the fluid dynamic model Δp_{model} and the measured pressure difference Δp_{exp} . The function \underline{F} was used as a constrain in the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\underline{\Delta p}_{model}, \underline{\zeta}} \quad & \left\| \left(\underline{\Delta p}_{model} - \underline{\Delta p}_{exp} \right) \right\|_2^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \\ \underline{F}(\dot{V}_{exp}, \omega_{imp,exp}, \underline{\Delta p}_{model}, \underline{\zeta}) &= \underline{0} \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

To solve this constrained optimization problem the packages JuMP.jl [7] and Ipopt.jl [8] were used in the Julia environment. JuMP.jl provides a modeling language for mathematical optimization while Ipopt.jl is an interior point optimizer for large scale optimization problems. The obtained $\underline{\zeta}_{opt}$ -parameters were used to calculate the pump characteristic curve for a arbitrary flow rate and impeller speed. To calculate the pump characteristic curves, for the estimated model parameters the equation $\underline{0} = \underline{F}(\dot{V}, \omega_{imp,exp}, \underline{\Delta p}, \underline{\zeta}_{opt})$ was solved for different flow rates within a chosen intervall and for the impeller speeds used in the experiments. The package NLSolve was used for that purpose.

3.3.3. Residence time behaviour

To solve the system of ODEs derived in Sec. 2.3 and A.1.6 with the experimental tracer concentration being the input $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$, the package DifferentialEquations.jl [9] was used in Julia. The experimental data is discrete, meaning that $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ is just defined at the time points where a measurement was taken. The ODE solver however requires a continuous input function. Therefore a linear interpolation was carried out using the package interpolations.jl. For this part of the thesis the reaction term was set zero in all of the model equations.

To take the distance between the photosensor PS 1 and inlet of the RMP and the distance between the outlet of the pump and photosensor PS 2 into account, those distances were handled as a plug flow reactor (PFR), with the lag time being the space time of the respective pipe element. Therefore a extrapolation (flat) was carried out. The described procedure is explained in the following scheme.

Fig. 3.3.: Scheme for the calculation of the tracer concentration at the output of the pump $c_{\text{out}}(t - \tau_{\text{PS2}})$ for the two different reactor models introduced in Sec. 2.3 and A.1.6.

For the compartment model, the impeller and side channel are each divided into 55 compartments. The breaker channel is divided into 5 compartments. The number of circulations C was calculated according to Sec. A.6 and the circulation flow \dot{V}_{circ} was evenly divided among the interacting compartments. Since the ratio of circulations to compartments is not always integer, an alternative approach was used to divide the circulations among the interacting vessels (cf. Fig. 2.4). The internal flow rates were calculated according to Eq. (2.3) and Eq. (2.4) respectively.

The tracer concentration $c_{\text{out}}(t - \tau_{\text{PS2}})$ was then compared to the experimental data $c_{\text{out,exp}}(t)$ obtained from the procedure described in Subsec. 3.2.2.

3.3.4. Determination of residence time distribution by deconvolution

As the input concentration does not follow an ideal step function the residence time distribution $E(t)$ cannot be directly determined from the experimental measurement. Instead an deconvolution method is used as proposed by Mills and Duduković [10]:

$$E(\omega) = \frac{\frac{C_{\text{out,exp}}(\omega)}{C_{\text{in,exp}}(\omega)}}{1 + \gamma \cdot \frac{H(\omega) \cdot H_{\text{conj}}(\omega)}{C_{\text{in,exp}}(\omega) \cdot C_{\text{in,exp,conj}}(\omega)}} \quad (3.2)$$

With $E(\omega)$, $C_{\text{in,exp}}(\omega)$, $C_{\text{out,exp}}(\omega)$ and $H(\omega)$ being the discrete fast fourier transform (DFFT) of $E(t)$, $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$, $c_{\text{out,exp}}(t)$ and $h(t)$, respectively. The function $h(t)$ describes a second order smoothing series and is defined by $h(t) = [1, -2, 1, 0, \dots, 0]$ [11, 12]. The smoothing factor γ can take any value between 0 and ∞ . A method to obtain γ is also described in [10] and is summarized in Sec. A.7. $E(t)$ can then be calculated by performing a inverse DFFT (iDFFT) of Eq. (3.2). To implement the DFFT and iDFFT algorithms in Julia, the FFTW.jl package is used and since the experimental data is of discrete nature the functions rfft and irfft were utilized.

As a proof of concept the residence time distribution $E(t)$ obtained by the method described in this subsection is convolved with the measured input $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ to calculate the output $c_{\text{out,conv}}(t)$. To perform the convolution first the DFFT of $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ and $E(t)$ is computed. In the frequency domain the convolution in the time domain becomes a multiplication. Hence $C_{\text{out}}(\omega) = C_{\text{in,exp}}(\omega) \cdot E(\omega)$. $c_{\text{out}}(t)$ was then be calculated be computing the iDFFT of $C_{\text{out}}(\omega)$.

3.4. Simulative study of the reaction behaviour of the RMP

To compare the reaction behavior of the RMP to the behaviour of a CSTR, a simulation was carried out using both the compartment- and the CSTR-model. For this purpose, a reaction term $\underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{rr}$ was used in the model equations contrary to the previous conducted investigations, where the reaction term was ignored.

The following reaction network consisting of a main I and a secondary reaction II was selected for the simulation:

The reaction rate rr_{I} of the first reaction can be described by $rr_{\text{I}}(t) = k_{\text{I}} \cdot c_{\text{A}}(t) \cdot c_{\text{B}}(t)$ and the reaction rate rr_{II} of the second reaction by $rr_{\text{II}}(t) = k_{\text{I}} \cdot c_{\text{A}}^2(t)$.

The reaction network was chosen due to the fact that a reaction system with an unwanted side reaction that is of higher order with respect to the reactants is sensitive to the degree of backmixing in the reactor. The highest selectivity to the desired product C is achieved when the reaction is carried out in an ideal CSTR. Deviations from ideally backmixed reactors directly lead to a decrease of the selectivity. Thus, the selectivity of C in relation to A is a perfect indicator to assess the degree of backmixing in the RMP.

For simulating the reactions, the left side of the model equations was set to zero, since the steady-state operation was of interest. The reaction rate constants $k_{\text{I}}, k_{\text{II}}$ for both reactions were varied between 10^{-3} and $10^1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

To find the zero of the model functions, the package NLSolve.jl was used in Julia.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Fluid dynamical investigation

4.1.1. Estimation of the parameters used in the fluid dynamic model

Fig. 4.1 shows the experimental pump characteristic curves together with the pump characteristic curves obtained by fitting the fluid dynamic model to the experimental data. The respective parameters are summarized in Tab. 4.1.

Fig. 4.1.: Pressure increase of the pump as a function of the flow rate for different rotational speeds. Symbols: experimental data. Lines: fluid dynamic model fitted to experimental data.

Fig. 4.1 shows that the fluid dynamic model is capable of describing the pumps fluid dynamical behaviour over a large working range. However it can be seen that at the lowest rotational speed the deviation between the experimental data and the model increases. As pointed out by Eberweiser [3], this behaviour can occur due to the used pump housing made of PMMA. While the PMMA housing requires a teflon seal, the original metal housing does not require additional sealing. The additional seal alternates the pump geometry. However this change in the geometry is not considered in the fluid dynamic model, in which the geometrical parameters except the curvature of the impeller blades, and their thickness and the thickness of the impeller tip are obtained from the data sheet of the pump.

The thickness of the impeller blades, the impeller tip were measured using a calliper. Since the impeller's curvature could not be measured, it had to be calculated from other parameters, including the thickness of the impellers tip, hence it is affected by propagation of the measurement error. However this should effect all pump curves and not the pump curve with the lowest impeller speed in particular.

The ζ -parameters obtained for the investigated RMP400 via fitting the fluid dynamic model to the experimental pump curves are of the same order of magnitude as the respective ζ -values obtained in [3] for the smaller RMP80:

Tab. 4.1.: Value of the ζ -parameters obtained in this work for the RMP400 in comparison to RMP80 obtained in [3]. The table also contains the 97.5 % trust region, respectively. The trust regions were calculated according to [13].

Parameter	RMP400	RMP80 [3]
$\zeta_{sc,opt}$	107.545 ± 11.389	84.627 ± 27.418
$\zeta_{circ,opt}$	0.333 ± 0.008	0.364 ± 0.046
$\zeta_{bc,opt}$	0.178 ± 0.115	0.199 ± 0.171

In fact Tab. 4.1 indicates, that the $\zeta_{circ,opt}$ -values and $\zeta_{bc,opt}$ -values of the two RMPs are very close to each other. Taking into account the confidence interval, the ζ -parameters for both RMPs agree.

4.1.2. Parametrical sensitivity of the fluid dynamic model

To investigate the sensitivity of the pump characteristic curves to the different parameters ζ_{sc} , ζ_{circ} and ζ_{bc} , every ζ_{opt} -value was varied by multiplying it with a weighing factor g while the other two ζ -parameters were kept constant at their optimum (cf. Tab. 4.1). The following figure shows the relative deviation of the objective function of the optimization problem (cf. Eq. (3.1)) when varying the value of the respective ζ -parameter.

Fig. 4.2.: Sensitivity of the fluid dynamic model to the different ζ -parameters used. The respective ζ -parameter is weighted with the weighing factor g , while the other two were kept at the optimum (cf. Tab. 4.1).

Fig. 4.2 depicts that the fluid dynamic model has different sensitivities for each parameter, whereby the model is least sensitive to ζ_{bc} . Nevertheless, a change of its value by $\pm 10\%$ leads to a relative deviation of 20% from the optimum value at $g = 1$. In contrast the model shows the highest sensitivity to the ζ_{circ} -parameter, i.e. the loss coefficient of the circulation flow. Here even small changes increase the relative error tremendously.

The same observation, i.e. the same order regarding the models sensitivity to the respective ζ -parameter was also made in [3]. The narrowest confidence interval is shown by the ζ_{circ} -parameter (cf. Tab. 4.1). Thus, the considered confidence interval deviates only by approx. $\pm 2.47\%$ from its optimum. Consistent with the previous observations (cf. Fig. 4.2), the same order is observed with respect to the sensitivity of the fluid dynamic model to the various ζ -values. This can be seen from the fact that the ζ_{circ} , to which the fluid dynamic model is most sensitive, has the narrowest confidence interval. With decreasing sensitivity, the respective confidence interval widens.

4.1.3. Efficiency of the RMP

An aspect that must also be taken into account in the fluid dynamical investigation is the efficiency of the RMP η , which describes the ratio of fluid dynamic and mechanical energy input. If the efficiency of the pump is not given by the manufacturer, it has to be determined experimentally. For this purpose the torque T of the pump shaft is required. Although it was not possible to measure the torque directly within the scope of this work, the torque can be estimated from the motor characteristic curve for a given rotational speed f_{imp} and driving-frequency f_{AC} . The motor characteristic curve plots the rotational speed against the torque for a particular driving-frequency (i.e. the frequency of the AC-current driving the motor) [14]. Since the motor is operated in the linear range of the motor characteristic curve, the slope of the characteristic curve can be estimated from two points. Usually, the data sheet of the motor specifies the rated rotational speed f_{imp} and power P (at a driving-frequency of 50 Hz). With these values, the rated torque T_{rated} can be determined from the following equation:

$$M_{\text{rated}} = \frac{P_{\text{rated}}}{2\pi \cdot f_{\text{imp,rated}}} = \frac{P_{\text{rated}}}{\omega_{\text{imp,rated}}} \quad (4.1)$$

A second point of the motor characteristic curve is the rotational speed $f_{\text{imp},0}$, at which the motor is operated at idle speed, i.e. no torque is applied. A list of $f_{\text{imp},0}$ speeds for different driving-frequencies was supplied by the workshops of the RPTU.

The slope of the motor characteristic curve can then be calculated by the following equation:

$$s = \frac{0 - T_{\text{rated}}}{f_{\text{imp},0,f_{\text{AC}}=50 \text{ Hz}} - f_{\text{imp,rated}}} \quad (4.2)$$

When altering the driving-frequency at the frequency converter (driving-frequency \propto driving-voltage) to change the rotational speed of the impeller, the whole motor torque speed curve is shifted to the left or right, hence its slope does not change [14]. From this consideration, the following equation can be derived, from which, at a given rotational speed and driving-frequency, the torque can be determined:

$$T = -s \cdot (f_{\text{imp},0,f_{\text{AC}}} - f_{\text{imp}}) \quad (4.3)$$

Taking these considerations into account, the efficiency η of the RMP is then defined by:

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{exp}} \cdot \Delta p_{\text{exp}}}{-s \cdot (f_{\text{imp},0,f_{\text{AC}}} - f_{\text{imp,exp}})} \quad (4.4)$$

The following figure shows the efficiencies calculated from the experimental data using the proposed method.

Fig. 4.3.: Efficiency of the RMP for different rotational speeds, calculated by the method proposed in this work. As a guide to the eye, the experimental data is connected via linear interpolation.

Fig. 4.3 shows that the efficiencies of the RMP are very low, which would be problematic if conveying the reaction medium were the main task of the reaction mixing pump. However, for the RMP as a reactor, mixing is also very important and thus the low efficiency is not problematic. The efficiencies observed in Fig. 4.3 fit into the characteristic field of larger pumps [15] considering the scale effect [16]. The low efficiencies can be explained by the high friction losses that occur in the reaction mixing pump. Of particular note are gap losses, whose influence was investigated in [17].

As pointed out in Subsec. 4.1.1 the original pump housing was replaced by a PMMA-housing, which made the use of a teflon seal obligatory. Since the compressive strength of PMMA is significantly lower than that of stainless steel, the pump housing was tightened with a lower torque (16 N m) than specified by the manufacturer (54-83 N m). In combination with the teflon seal, which has a certain thickness, a larger gap is therefore to be expected within the experimental setup than when the stainless steel housing is used for the pump.

4.1.4. Internal flow characteristics of the pump

To estimate the mixing behavior within the pump, internal volume flow ratios are suitable. For this purpose the ζ -parameters obtained from fitting the fluid dynamic model to the experimental pump characteristic curves can be used. The flow ratios that resulted for the investigated working range are listed in the following table (cf. Tab. 4.2):

Tab. 4.2.: Internal volume flow fractions of the RMP for the investigated working range.

Fraction	Minimum	Maximum
$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}}$	0.050	0.050
$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}}$	0.005	0.042
$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}}$	1.342	96.839

It must be taken into account that the maximum recycle ratio occurred in combination with the two minimal circulation ratios and vice versa.

From Tab. 4.2 it can be seen that the circulation ratio in the side and impeller channel is always significantly smaller than 1, which means that the flow rate of the circulation \dot{V}_{circ} is significantly larger than the flow rate in the impeller channel \dot{V}_{imp} and in the side channel \dot{V}_{sc}^* . This means that the cross flow within the pump must be significantly greater than the flow in the axial direction. This cross flow contributes significantly to the mixing performance of the RMP. Tab. 4.2 also indicates, that $\dot{V}_{\text{imp}} \cdot \dot{V}_{\text{circ}}^{-1}$ does not depend on the operating point since it is constant for the observed working range.

Furthermore, it can be seen from Tab. 4.2, that in the investigated working range of the pump the recycle ratio is always greater than 1, which means that the recirculated volume flow is greater than the pumped volume flow, which also contributes positively to the mixing performance of the pump.

By superimposing these two effects, a mixing flow regime occurs throughout the pump. The mixing behaviour improves at high pressures in combination with low flow rates, which was also observed in [3] for the smaller RMP.

Eq. (2.7) and (2.8) consist of a term which only depends on the geometrical parameters of the pump. For two pumps that have a geometric similarity, all dimensions are multiplied by a constant factor. This factor is cancelled out in Eq. (2.7) and (2.8), which means that the pumps

geometry should not influence the flow ratios and thus the mixing behaviour when the pump is scaled up.

From the consideration to characterize the mixing behavior of the RMP by flow rate fractions a system of equations can be derived (cf. Sec. A.8), in which the individual equations only depend on the geometry and the ζ -parameters obtained in Subsec. 4.1.1:

$$\xi_{\text{sc,imp,opt}} \leq \min \left[\sqrt{\frac{a-b}{a}}; \frac{a}{\sqrt{c^2+a^2}}; \frac{b}{d} \right] \quad (4.5)$$

With

- $a = 4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)}$
- $b = V_{\text{imp}}$
- $c = A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*$
- $d = V_{\text{sc}} \cdot \frac{360}{\varphi_{\text{sc}}}$

The minimum described by Eq. (4.5) describes a maximum $\xi_{\text{sc,imp,opt}}$ value at which backmixing and crossmixing are guaranteed, which means that for the determined $\xi_{\text{sc,imp,opt}}$ the following equations apply:

- $\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{V_{\text{circ}}} \leq 1$
- $\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{V_{\text{circ}}} \leq 1$
- $\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{V_{\text{in}}} \geq 1$

The ξ -value calculated by the proposed way can then be used to delimit operating ranges with regard to the degree of mixing. A potential approach to represent these ranges is shown in Fig. 4.4. The diagram depicts that the mixing behaviour only depends on the backmixing, which is due to the fact that the evaluation of Eq. (4.5) showed that the minimum of the equation can be described by the last term ($b \cdot d^{-1}$). Hence the circulation ratio is always smaller than one, and thus sufficient crossmixing can always be assumed for a recycle ratio larger than one. The operating range of the pump can therefore be divided into different backmixing zones, which is shown in Fig. 4.4.

Fig. 4.4.: Pump characteristic curves (obtained from the fluid dynamic model) with different backmixing regions. Red zone: strongly backmixed, grey zone: backmixed, green zone: weakly backmixed, yellow zone: insufficiently backmixed. The division into the individual zones was done at the discretion of the author.

Fig. 4.4 indicates, that the desired grade of backmixing can be set by adjusting the operating point (e.g. by a throttle valve). The division into the different zones was chosen arbitrarily. The idea was to define a zone in which the recycle ratio is less than 1 (yellow area in Fig. 4.4) and therefore the volume inside the RMP is insufficiently backmixed. The further classification was made at the author's discretion according to weakly backmixed (green area), backmixed (grey area) and strongly backmixed (red area). It can be expected that with increased backmixing the reaction mixing pump behaves more like a CSTR.

4.2. Characterization of the RMP as a reactor

4.2.1. Comparison between predicted and experimental residence time behaviour

The results of the reaction engineering investigation are shown in the following figure. Fig. 4.5 also contains the concentration at the outlet of the pump predicted by the reactor models derived in Sec. 2.3 and A.1.6.

Fig. 4.5.: Measured and predicted residence time behaviour of the RMP at different operating points. Symbols: measured concentration of tracer: (dots) inlet (crosses) outlet. Lines: predicted concentration of tracer at the outlet, (solid) compartment model parameterized in this work, (dashed) ideal CSTR.

Fig. 4.5 depicts the comparison of the measured and predicted response of the RMP to a step input of the tracer. In Fig. 4.5 it can be seen that the concentration at the outlet $c_{\text{out,exp}}(t)$ increases much slower than the concentration at the inlet $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$, which can be explained by the strong crossmixing in combination with the high recycle ratio. The maximum concentration at the outlet is reached shortly after reaching the maximum concentration at the inlet. Afterwards, the concentration at the outlet slowly decreases, which is called tailing. The tailing can be caused, for example, by stagnant zones whose volume is exchanged slower than in the rest of the volume.

In Fig. 4.5 it can be seen, that for all cases, except for B), the residence time behaviour can be better predicted by the compartment model than by the CSTR model. This can be explained with previous observations made in Subsec. 4.1.4. At low flow rates according to the fluid dynamic model, higher backmixing is present in the RMP. High backmixing causes the RMP to behave more like an ideal CSTR, as opposed to low backmixing. In contrast to the previous work [3], where there was no difference between the prediction of the initial concentration via CSTR and compartment model, significant differences between the two models are evident for the investigated RMP in this work. In general, a better agreement between model and experiment is presented at low flow rates, while at higher flow rates a greater deviation between the model and experimental data can be observed. However at this point it must be emphasized, that the model is purely predictive, which means that no parameters of the model were fitted to experimental data but obtained from the fluid dynamic model of the RMP.

One reason for the large deviation at higher flow rates could be that the pressure losses in the breaker channel of the RMP are underestimated at higher flow rates, which means that ζ_{bc} is actually lower. The underestimation of the friction losses in the breaker channel lead to an overestimation of the flow rate in the side channel \dot{V}_{sc} (cf. Eq. (2.4)). In the conception of the RMP as an interconnection of individual compartments, the overestimated side channel flow rate results in a portion of the injected tracer passing through the pump faster than it is the case in reality. This can be seen in the left half of Fig. 4.5, where the concentration at the outlet estimated by the compartment model increases faster than the measured concentration at the outlet.

The gap of the pump (cf. Fig. 3.2), i.e. the distance between the impeller and the pump housing, is not considered in any of the models. In reality, the RMP has a certain stagnant volume due to this gap. If tracer is now fed into the pump, this dead region is also filled with tracer and must be replaced, which can be recognized by the tailing, i.e. the slow decay of the measured concentration in the outlet, compared to the modeled outlet concentrations of the RMP (cf. Fig. 4.5). The exchange of stagnant volume can take place via various mechanisms. One consideration here is that some of the stagnant volume is sucked out of the dead region by the circulation flow similar to the operation principle of a water jet pump, which is illustrated in Fig. 4.6.

Fig. 4.6.: Flow from the stagnant zone inside the RMP due to the circulation. The circulation reduces the static pressure at the interface between the gap and the side channel, which causes the death volume to be pulled out of the gap channel, similar to the working principle of a water jet pump.

If this is the case, the volume flow from the death region (green arrow in Fig. 4.6) would be significantly influenced by the circulation flow. The circulation flow in return depends largely on the speed of the impeller and the geometry of the pump, but hardly on the side channel speed, since $\omega_{\text{imp}} > \omega_{\text{sc}}$ (cf. Eq. (2.3)).

If the flow rate is increased at a constant impeller speed, only the flow rate of the side channel increases, while the circulation flow remains approximately the same. Thus, only the time constant of the convective mass transport decreases while the time constant describing the flow from the stagnant volume into the side-channel remains the same. Since the ratio of the time constants describing the respective mass transport increases, the influence of the gap which is not taken into account also increases, which could lead to the bigger deviations observed at higher flow rates.

4.2.2. Parametrical sensitivity of the compartment model

Since the compartment model depends on the ζ -parameters determined in Subsec. 4.1.1, the influence of these parameters on the reactor model is examined. However, since the model only depends on the ζ_{circ} -parameter and the ζ_{bc} -parameter, solely their influence is examined. The sensitivity of the compartment model to these parameters is tested by varying the parameters by its respective confidence interval (cf Tab. 4.1).

Fig. 4.7.: Sensitivity of the compartment model to the different ζ -parameters. The left side refers to variations of ζ_{circ} and the right side to variations of ζ_{bc} . The respective ζ -parameter was varied by \pm of its confidence interval (cf. Tab. 4.1). For a better overview, the experimental data at the outlet of the pump is also shown. All shown graphs represent data at an impeller speed f_{imp} of 29.4 s^{-1} .

To illustrate the sensitivity of the compartment model to the parameters, six concentration curves are shown in Fig. 4.7. The left graphs describe the influence of the ζ_{circ} -parameter and the right the influence of the ζ_{bc} -parameter. The respective ζ -parameter was changed by its confidence interval $\Delta\zeta$ (cf. Tab. 4.1).

In the left half of Fig. 4.7, it can be seen that the compartment model is not sensitive to the ζ_{circ} -parameter, while the fluid dynamic model which describes the pump characteristic curves is very sensitive to this parameter (cf. Fig. 4.2). In contrast, the compartment model is more sensitive to the ζ_{bc} -parameter, which can be seen in the right half of Fig. 4.7.

At high flow rates, the difference between model and experimental data can be reduced by lowering the ζ_{bc} -parameter. Since the measured concentration at the output $c_{\text{out,exp}}(t)$ lays between two of the predicted concentration curves (cf. graph B) and D) in Fig. 4.7), it can be assumed that there exist a ζ_{bc} -parameter in the range of the trust region, for which the concentration at the output can be predicted more accurately.

This improvement for a lower ζ_{bc} -parameter could suggest that the losses in the breaker channel are underestimated. However, a reduction of the ζ_{bc} -parameter at low flow rates leads to a larger deviation between model and experimental data (cf. graph F) in Fig. 4.7). This could indicate that the gap between the pump casing and the impeller has an influence on the mass transfer within the pump as pointed out in the previous section. The compartment model could be modified in the future to explicitly consider the stagnant volume in the gap region.

4.2.3. Reconstructing the residence time distribution by deconvolution

As explained in Subsec. A.1.5, the residence time distribution $E(t)$ can be determined by deconvolution of an arbitrary input signal with the output signal. The results of the deconvolution are shown in the left side of the following figure for three different operating points.

As a proof of concept the right side of Fig. 4.8 contains the concentration at the output obtained by convolution of the experimental input concentration $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ with the respective $E(t)$. For comparison the figure also shows the experimental concentration at the output $c_{\text{out,exp}}(t)$. Fig. 4.8 also contains the smoothing factor γ used in each case, which was determined according to the procedure described in Sec. A.7.

Fig. 4.8.: Left half: Residence time distribution $E(\theta)$ obtained by the deconvolution method described in [10]. Right half: $c_{\text{out,con}}(t)$ computed by convolution of $E(\theta)$ (shown on the left side of the figure) with the measured concentration at the inlet of the pump $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ and for comparison also the experimental data at the outlet (crosses). All shown graphs represent data at an impeller speed f_{imp} of 29.4 s^{-1} . The left graphs also contain the smoothing factor γ used for the deconvolution, respectively. θ is defined as $\frac{t}{\bar{\tau}}$

The residence time distribution of the RMP (cf. left side of Fig. 4.8) cannot be assigned to either one of the two ideal reactor types discussed in Subsec. A.1.6. Rather, it can be assumed that $E(t)$ is determined by superposition of the several mixing effects, which were discussed in Subsec. 4.1.4. The behaviour of the RMP for lower flow rates can rather be assigned to that of a CSTR (increased cross flow \rightarrow increased mixing), than the behaviour at higher flow rates.

It can be seen on the left side of Fig. 4.8, this peaks occur in the residence time distribution $E(t)$ indicating a strong recirculation [18]. The peaks are distinct at higher flow rates, which could indicate a more PFR-like behaviour of the RMP in combination with a distinct recycle ratio. At lower flow rates a flattening of these peaks i.e. a smoothing of the $E(t)$ curve can be observed. The smoothing at low flow rates could be explained by the increased crossmixing and can be associated with a more CSTR-like behaviour of the RMP. However, it must be emphasized that the fluctuations can also be artifacts of the deconvolution, and therefore cannot be clearly attributed to the mixing behavior. One argument in favor of the artifacts that occur due to the deconvolution is that the peaks do not occur synchronously with the circulation time.

By using a smoothing term during deconvolution, the noise that would normally occur when applying Eq. (3.2) without smoothing (i.e. $\gamma = 0$) can be adequately filtered out (an example for an unfiltered result can be seen in Sec. A.7). This allows reasonable results to be obtained for the residence time distribution even if the input is not an impulse or an ideal step. However, the influence of the smoothing factor still needs to be further investigated, since its choice is in principle arbitrary. The smoothing factor must always be chosen high enough to filter out noise and low enough to preserve important properties of the residence time distribution. Furthermore, it should be ensured that only reasonable values for $E(t)$ are obtained by the choice of the smoothing factor γ , e.g. that $E(t)$ cannot become negative.

The concentration at the output, obtained by convolving $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ with $E(t)$ matches the concentration measured at the output $c_{\text{out,exp}}$ with only small deviations occurring (cf. right side of Fig. 4.8).

4.2.4. Simulation of the reactive behaviour of the RMP

Although the residence time behaviour of the RMP could already be characterized in the previous sections, it must be noted that no meaningful conclusions about the reactive behaviour can yet be drawn there of. This is due to the fact that two reactor systems that have the same RTD can have a different behaviour when a chemical reaction takes place in these systems [1].

To investigate the reactive behavior of the RMP, a simulation study was performed, adding a reactive term to the model equations of the compartment model. For comparison, the same reaction was simulated in an ideal CSTR. Four different operating points were investigated for the simulation, with the impeller speed set to 60 % of the nominal speed. When selecting the operating points, care was taken to ensure that all three mixing ranges (cf. Fig. 4.4) were covered. For a better overview, the simulation results of only one operating point are shown in this section, while the other simulation results can be found in Sec. A.9.

Sec. A.9 also lists the respective operating points (cf. Tab. A.2). The results shown in this section refer to the operating point B in Tab. A.2 and therefore to the backmixed region in Fig. A.14 (green area). In order to be within a reasonable range in terms of conversion, the inlet concentration of both reactants A and B were set to 10 mol L^{-1} . The simulated reaction network was chosen for the reason that in this reaction the selectivity of the target product is sensitive to the backmixing and therefore differences between the two types of reactors (RMP vs. CSTR) should be revealed by the simulation. To characterize the behaviour, the following figure shows the relative conversion (which means in this case relative to the conversion in an ideal CSTR with the same properties as the RMP) as a function of the reaction rate constants of the main k_I and the secondary reaction k_{II} . For a better overview, the conversions in the ideal CSTR are also shown in Fig. 4.9 as black and grey lines.

Fig. 4.9.: Relative conversion $\left(\frac{X_{\text{Comp,A}}}{X_{\text{CSTR,A}}}\right)$ for the simulated reaction network (cf. Sec. 3.4) as a function of the two reaction rate constants k_I and k_{II} . The figure also contains the conversion in the CSTR $X_{\text{CSTR,A}}$ (lines) with its respective value. Shown are the simulation results of the operating point where the recycle ratio is between 2 and 4, and therefore in the backmixed region.

First of all, it can be seen that the difference between the CSTR and the compartment model is greater at smaller conversions. This means, for example, that at 60 % conversion in the CSTR, the conversion of a reaction mixing pump operated under the same conditions is approx. 8 % higher, and is thus approx. 65 %, while at a conversion of 90 % in the CSTR the conversion in the RMP is only approx. 92 %. However, it must be taken into account that the larger difference is weighted less strongly for small conversions which can be explained in the following way:

At 10 % conversion in the ideal CSTR, the conversion in the reaction mixing pump is 22 % higher, and thus is 12.2 %. This means, that at this conversion with the concentration of A at the inlet being at 10 mol/l, the concentration at the outlet of the RMP is 8.8 mol L^{-1} while for the CSTR it would be 9.0 mol L^{-1} . The situation is analogous for large conversions. At 90 % conversion in the CSTR, the conversion in the RMP is only about 4 % higher, and is thus 93.6 %. At this conversion, the concentration at the outlet of the RMP would be 0.64 mol L^{-1} , while it would be 1.0 mol L^{-1} for the CSTR. Consequently, the absolute difference between reaction mixing pump and CSTR is greatest at medium conversions.

In general, the reaction mixing pump always has a higher conversion than the CSTR for the simulated reaction, even though the modeled residence time behaviour in Fig. 4.5 for the compartment-model and the CSTR model is very similar. However, no conclusions can be drawn from the conversion as to whether the reactants react to form the desired product, or the undesired by-product. In the simulation study prepared within the scope of this work, component C resembles the desired product and D the unwanted by-product. This means that a high conversion alone is not necessarily to be evaluated positively. Rather, in combination with the conversion, another key figure, the selectivity (cf. Eq. (A.3)), must be taken into account. For this purpose, the following figure shows the relative selectivity of C with respect to A as a function of the reaction rate constant (again, relative here means relative to the selectivity in the ideal CSTR). $S_{C,A}$ means specifically, the amount of A formed relative to the amount of C converted.

Fig. 4.10.: Relative sensitivity $\left(\frac{S_{\text{Comp,C,A}}}{S_{\text{CSTR,C,A}}}\right)$ for the simulated reaction network (cf. Sec. 3.4) as a function of the two reaction rate constants k_I and k_{II} . The figure also contains the selectivity in the CSTR $S_{\text{CSTR,C,A}}$ (black lines) with its respective value. Shown are the simulation results of the operating point where the recycle ratio is between 2 and 4, and therefore in the backmixed region.

Analogous to Fig. 4.9, the selectivity in the ideal CSTR is shown in Fig. 4.10 via black lines. Fig. 4.10 shows that the differences between the two models decrease at higher selectivity. As in the case of conversion, it can be observed that in most cases the RMP has a higher selectivity with respect to the target product A than the CSTR. However, it can be seen in Fig. 4.10 that below the 1st bisector there is hardly any difference between CSTR and RMP while the largest differences occur above the 1st bisector. Furthermore, a smaller deviation between the two reactor types is generally observed for selectivity than for conversion. Thus, the selectivity deviate by a maximum of 10 %, while the conversion deviates by up to 25 %.

It can be seen in Fig. 4.10 that the largest difference occurs when a very slow main reaction is accompanied by a very fast side reaction ($k_{II} \gg k_I$). However, the selectivity in this region is so low that it has no technical relevance. Furthermore, it can be observed in the upper right corner of Fig. 4.10 that the selectivity of the RMP is lower than that of the CSTR in this area. Hence, if the simplifying assumption was made to depict the RMP via a CSTR model instead

of a compartment model, the selectivity would be overestimated. The difference that occur in this area becomes smaller with decreasing flow rate, as the further simulation results show (cf. Sec. A.9). This observation supports the assumption that the reaction mixing pump behaves more like a CSTR at low flow rates.

As explained in Subsec. A.1.3, the yield in addition to the conversion and the selectivity plays an important role when describing a chemical reaction. For this purpose, the relative yield is shown in Fig. 4.11. The yield of the ideal CSTR is shown via the black lines for a better comparison.

Fig. 4.11.: Relative yield $\left(\frac{Y_{\text{Comp,C,A}}}{Y_{\text{CSTR,C,A}}}\right)$ for the simulated reaction network (cf. Sec. 3.4) as a function of the two reaction rate constants k_{I} and k_{II} . The figure also contains the yield in the CSTR $Y_{\text{CSTR,C,A}}$ (black lines) with its respective value. Shown are the simulation results of the operating point where the recycle ratio is between 2 and 4, and therefore in the backmixed region.

Since the yield is the product of conversion and selectivity (cf. Eq. (A.5)) and both conversion and selectivity are higher in the RMP, the yield in the RMP is also higher than in the ideal CSTR in the considered range of the reaction rate constant, which can be seen in Fig. 4.11. In summary, the RMP, for the considered reaction system generally performs better than an ideal CSTR with the same properties.

The simulation results are in agreement with the previous considerations postulated from the fluid dynamic model. At low flow rates (red area in Fig. 4.4), the fluid dynamic model predicts high backmixing, i.e. the volume of the RMP is generally better mixed. This increased degree of mixing leads to only small deviations between the CSTR and the RMP which could also be shown by the simulative study (cf. subplot A in Fig. A.15).

At higher flow rates, (green area in Fig. 4.4), the backmixing decreases. As a result, higher differences between the RMP and the CSTR must also occur, which could also be observed in the simulative study, as the subplot D in Fig. A.15 in the appendix shows.

5. Conclusion

In this work, fluid dynamical and reaction engineering properties of a reaction mixing pump were investigated.

First, a fluid dynamic model developed by Oliver Bey was used. This model is based on three parameters intended to describe friction losses within the pump. These parameters were obtained by fitting the fluid dynamic model to experimental pump characteristic curves, whereby it could be shown that the model is capable of describing the pump characteristic curves with high accuracy.

The sensitivity of the fluid dynamic model to the different parameters was examined to determine the impact of these parameters on the model. It could be shown that the model has different sensitivities to the individual parameters, with the fluid dynamic model being particularly sensitive to the loss coefficient, which describes the friction losses of the circulation flow ζ_{circ} . The different sensitivities of the model for the parameters led to the fact that these parameters are determined with different accuracy, which was also shown in this work. While the 97.5 % confidence interval of the parameter for which the model is most sensitive varies by only about 2.5 % of its optimal value, a much wider confidence interval was observed for the parameter for which the model is most insensitive. Whereby the value for this parameter fluctuates by up to approx. 64 % of its optimal value obtained by the fit.

Since this is not a satisfactory accuracy, it was already considered in a previous work [3] to develop a parameter based model that describes the efficiency of the RMP. To determine the parameters, the developed model would then be fitted to experimental efficiencies. In order to obtain the efficiency experimentally, the torque applied at the pump shaft is needed. In order to determine the torque, complex measurements are usually necessary. While it was neither possible to develop an appropriate model nor to measure the torque within the scope of this work, a method is proposed in this thesis to estimate torque from simple rotational speed measurements. The estimated torque could be used to determine the efficiency of the pump. The efficiencies obtained by the proposed method were very low and reach a maximum of approx. 10 %. However, they fit into the characteristic field of side channel machines [16], which describes the efficiency as a function of the specific speed. But it must be noted that only larger pumps were investigated in [16].

The parameters obtained from fitting the fluid dynamic model to experimental pump curves were used to calculate internal flow fractions. In the operating range investigated, the flow rate of the internal circulation is 20 times greater than the flow rate in the impeller and approx. 24 to 200 times greater than the flow rate in the side channel. While the flow of the impeller and side channel is in the axial direction, the circulation flow is transverse to it, resulting in crossmixing. Also, the recirculation flow rate is approx. 1.3 to 97 times larger than the conveyed flow, which positively contributes to backmixing.

This means that there is mainly a mixing flow regime in the RMP. The highest backmixing can be achieved at low flow rates in combination with high pressures differences and therefore also high impeller speeds.

The second part of the work investigated the reaction engineering properties of the RMP. For this purpose, the residence time behavior was first examined. Therefore tracer experiments were conducted using a dye which is detected and quantified by turbidity measurements at the inlet and outlet of the pump. A compartment model utilizing the parameters obtained by fitting the fluid dynamic model to experimental pump curves was used to predict the concentration of the dye at the outlet. The parameters were used to calculate the internal flow rates, i.e. the side channel flow rate and the circulation flow rate. However only two of the three ζ -parameters were needed. While the compartment model is capable of predicting the concentration at the outlet of the pump at low flow rates with a high accuracy, at higher flow rates, an increased deviation between the predicted and experimental data was observed.

Furthermore, the sensitivity of the compartment model to the ζ -parameters used was characterized. For this purpose, the parameters were changed by \pm of its 97.5% confidence interval, respectively. While the fluid dynamic model showed the highest sensitivity to ζ_{circ} , the compartment model was not sensitive to this parameter at all. However, the compartment model was found to be sensitive to ζ_{bc} , which is the parameter that can be determined most inaccurately by fitting the fluid dynamic model to experimental pump curves. At high flow rates, a decrease of ζ_{bc} led to a better prediction of the outlet concentration via the compartment model, whereas the concentration at the outlet of the pump was predicted more poorly for low flow rates. Hence no optimal value for ζ_{bc} with respect to the residence time behaviour can be determined.

In addition a method to accomplish the residence time distribution from the non-ideal input which corresponds neither to an impulse nor to an ideal jump was tested in the scope of this work. The course of the residence time distribution obtained in this way can be explained by the internal flow conditions and the concentration at the outlet of the pump can be estimated by convolving the inlet concentration with the residence time distribution determined by the used method with only minor deviations occurring.

Simulations were performed to investigate the behaviour of reactive systems in the RMP. A reactive system was selected that is composed of a main and secondary reaction. Second-order kinetics were chosen for both the main and side reaction, and the reaction rate constants of the two reactions were varied from 10^{-3} to 10^1 to cover a wide a range with respect to the conversion. For the simulation the compartment model was used to describe the RMP and extended by a reactive term. For comparison, the same simulation was conducted in an ideal CSTR with the same operating parameters as the RMP. It was found that the deviations between RMP and CSTR are minor at low flow rates, while higher deviations occurred at an increased flow rate. As proposed in this thesis, this could be due to the increased backmixing at low flow rates, which is associated with a more CSTR-like behaviour.

6. Outlook

To better determine the ζ_{bc} -parameter, it may be beneficial to develop a model that can predict the efficiency of peripheral pumps as a function of impeller speed, pressure, and flow rate. In this context, the method proposed in this thesis to estimate the torque could be utilized after investigations were aimed at verifying the respective method.

Further compartment models should also be examined, e.g. a model that explicitly takes into account the gaps inside the RMP. A simplification of the currently used model should also be investigated. In order to be able to determine the residence time distribution more precisely, it would also be interesting to optimize the test rig so that an ideal step can be realized more adequately. Comparatively, the determination of the residence time distribution by deconvolution of the output signal with the input signal could also be investigated, whereby especially a better method for the determination of the smoothing factor would be interesting here. Two-phase operation is also of interest in residence time distribution and should be investigated in subsequent papers.

Since in this thesis only one reaction network was investigated simulatively, further investigations should be aimed at in the future. On the one hand simulatively, e.g. by variation of the reaction order, and on the other hand experimentally whereby especially mixing-sensitive reactions are of great interest. An overview of such reactions can be found in [19, 20]. The reactions listed in the latter were tested suitable for characterizing the mixing behaviour of reactors by Hecht *et al.* [20]. In the course of this, the test rig should be optimized to allow quantification of the reactants at the in- and outlet of the pump. Furthermore, the test reactions and conditions should be selected in such a way that neither a full conversion nor no conversion takes place in the RMP, since at the present time no spatial resolution of the concentration in the reaction mixing pump is possible.

An advantage of the RMP, which could be determined in this and in the previous work, is that the mixing behaviour can be adjusted via the flow rate, which can be associated with a significant increase in process flexibility. This high degree of flexibility makes it easier to adapt faster to fluctuations in the composition of the reactant and also to fluctuations in the energy supply, which will occur more frequently in the future due to the increasing use of renewable energies.

Bibliography

- [1] R. Güttel and T. Turek, *Chemische Reaktionstechnik*, ger, 1. Aufl. 2021. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2021, 335 pp., Güttel, Robert (VerfasserIn) Turek, Thomas (VerfasserIn), ISBN: 978-3-662-63150-8. [Online]. Available: <http://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:bsz:31-epflicht-1867070>.
- [2] A. Fleder, *Reaktionsmischpumpe, Aufbau einer Reaktionsmischpumpe und Mitarbeit bei der Entwicklung eines Strömungsmodells*, Lehrstuhl für Strömungsmechanik und Strömungsmaschinen, Jul. 2020.
- [3] S. Eberweiser, “Experimentelle Untersuchung der fluiddynamischen Eigenschaften von Reaktionsmischpumpen zur Beurteilung ihrer Betriebsbereiche,” Lehrstuhl für Reaktions- und Fluidverfahrenstechnik, Masterarbeit, TU Kaiserslautern, 2022.
- [4] KSB SE & Co. KGaA, Ed. “Seitenkanalpumpe.” (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.ksb.com/de-global/kreiselpumpenlexikon/artikel/seitenkanalpumpe-1104388>.
- [5] G. H. Grabow and N. D. Suong, “Berechnungsmodell zur Auslegung von Seitenkanalmaschinen,” *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen*, vol. 58, no. 11-12, pp. 273–282, 1992, PII: BF02560552, ISSN: 0015-7899. DOI: 10.1007/BF02560552.
- [6] E. Muschelknautz, “Untersuchungen an Seitenkanalmaschinen,” in *Seitenkanal-Strömungsmaschinen*, W. H. Faragallah, Ed., 1. Aufl., Sulzbach/Ts.: W. H. Faragallah, 1992, pp. 402–420, ISBN: 392968201X.
- [7] I. Dunning, J. Huchette, and M. Lubin, “Jump: A modeling language for mathematical optimization,” *SIAM Review*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 295–320, 2017, ISSN: 0036-1445. DOI: 10.1137/15M1020575.
- [8] Stefan Vigerske and Andreas Wächter. “Ipopt documentation.” (), [Online]. Available: <https://coin-or.github.io/Ipopt/>.
- [9] Christopher Rackauckas, Michael Hatherly, The Gitter Badger, Max G, and Kvaz1r, *Juliadiffeq/differentialequations.jl: Add modeling packages*, Zenodo, 2017. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.283869.
- [10] P. L. Mills and M. P. Duduković, “Convolution and deconvolution of nonideal tracer response data with application to three-phase packed-beds,” *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 881–898, 1989, PII: 0098135489850628, ISSN: 00981354. DOI: 10.1016/0098-1354(89)85062-8.
- [11] K. Abou Hweij and F. Azizi, “Hydrodynamics and residence time distribution of liquid flow in tubular reactors equipped with screen-type static mixers,” *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 279, pp. 948–963, 2015, PII: S1385894715007883, ISSN: 13858947. DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2015.05.100.

- [12] Z.-S. MAO, T. XIONG, and J. CHEN, “Residence time distribution of liquid flow in a trickle bed evaluated using fft deconvolution,” *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 169, no. 1, pp. 223–244, 1998, ISSN: 0098-6445. DOI: 10.1080/00986449808912730.
- [13] *Mathematical modeling in chemical engineering*, Online-Ausg. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015, ISBN: 978-1-107-04969-7. DOI: 10.1017/CB09781107279124.
- [14] M. Doppelbauer, *Grundlagen der Elektromobilität*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2020, ISBN: 978-3-658-29729-9. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-29730-5.
- [15] N.-H. D. Karlsen-Davies, “Computational and experimental analysis of the effects of manufacturing tolerances on the performance of a regenerative liquid ring pump,” Dissertation, Lancaster University, 2017.
- [16] G. Grabow, “Optimalbereiche von Fluidenergiemaschinen-Pumpen und Verdichter,” *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 100–106, 2002, PII: H1FW7H8YT58HPGEW, ISSN: 0015-7899. DOI: 10.1007/s10010-002-0084-1.
- [17] A. Fleder and M. Böhle, “A systematical study of the influence of blade length, blade width, and side channel height on the performance of a side channel pump,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, vol. 137, no. 12, 2015, ISSN: 0098-2202. DOI: 10.1115/1.4030897.
- [18] O. Levenspiel, *Chemical reaction engineering*, eng, 3. ed. New York and Weinheim: Wiley, 1999, 668 pp., ISBN: 978-0-471-25424-9.
- [19] J. R. Bourne, “Mixing and the selectivity of chemical reactions,” *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 471–508, 2003, ISSN: 1083-6160. DOI: 10.1021/op020074q.
- [20] K. J. Hecht, A. Kölbl, M. Kraut, and K. Schubert, “Micromixer characterization with competitive-consecutive bromination of 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene,” *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 1176–1181, 2008, ISSN: 09307516. DOI: 10.1002/ceat.200800213.
- [21] D. Surek, “Pumpen,” in *Handbuch Maschinenbau*, A. Böge and W. Böge, Eds., Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2021, pp. 1039–1053, ISBN: 978-3-658-30272-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-30273-3_54.
- [22] A. Böge and W. Böge, Eds., *Handbuch Maschinenbau*, Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2021, ISBN: 978-3-658-30272-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-30273-3.
- [23] KSB SE & Co. KGaA, Ed. “Mechanische Leistung.” (), [Online]. Available: <https://www.ksb.com/de-global/kreiselpumpenlexikon/artikel/mechanische-leistung-1100612>.
- [24] E. von Harbou, *Vorlesung chemische Verfahrenstechnik (Wintersemester 2023)*, Lehrstuhl für Reaktions- und Fluidverfahrenstechnik, collab. [Online]. Available: <https://mv.rptu.de/fgs/lrf/lehre/veranstaltungen/sommersemester-23/chemische-verfahrenstechnik>.
- [25] *VDI-Wärmeatlas*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013, ISBN: 978-3-642-19980-6. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-19981-3.

- [26] H. Ulrich and H. Weber, *Laplace-, Fourier- und z-Transformation*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2017, ISBN: 978-3-658-03449-8. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-658-03450-4.
- [27] P. K Mogensen and A. N Riseth, “Optim: A mathematical optimization package for julia,” *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 3, no. 24, p. 615, 2018. DOI: 10.21105/joss.00615.

A. Appendix

A.1. Supplementary theoretical background

A.1.1. Pumps

Pumps are machines which rise the total energy level of liquids by supplying mechanical energy. The energy input is converted into potential energy (e.g. by raising the height, also called pump head, of a watercolumn) and into kinetic energy (e.g. by maintaining a certain flow rate of the liquid). The equivalent to transport gases are called compressors. However some pumps can transport liquids containing a certain amount of gas. [21]

Fig. A.1.: Charakteristic map of positive displacement and flow pumps. Own illustration according to [21].

Pumps in general can be classified into two types. Positive displacement pumps and flow pumps. The former type of pumps is characterized by spatially separated volumes. Positive displacement pumps in general deliver higher pump heads than flow pumps.

Flow pumps on the other hand convey liquids by using fluid dynamic principles. Flow pumps have an impeller and can be distinguished by the impellers design and by the positioning of the in- and outlet (e.g. radial, axial, etc.). Due to the impeller, flow pumps are also called centrifugal pumps.

Pumps have a specific conveying behaviour. When driven with a constant rotational speed f_{imp} with decreasing flow rate the pump head increases. This behaviour can be shown in a certain type of diagram, a so called pump characteristic curve. In this diagrams the pump head, or respectively the pressure difference between in- and outlet of the pump is plotted against the

flow rate for different impeller speeds. Pump characteristic curves come in handy when comparing different pumps among each other.

Fig. A.2.: Pump characteristic curves (solid lines) and an exemplary system characteristic curve (dashed line), with the operation point at the intersection of pump and system characteristic curve. Own illustration according to [21].

Another curve shown in Fig. A.2 is the so called system characteristic curve, which plots the pressure loss of the system in which the pump is integrated against the flow. The intersection of pump and system characteristic curve is the operating point. Therefore the flow of the pump can be set by altering the system curve, e.g. by the use of a throttle valve.

A.1.2. Efficiency of Pumps

The efficiency η of a pump describes the ratio of effective power P_E and shaft power P_S . The effective power is defined via $P_E = \dot{V} \cdot \Delta p$. [22]

The shaft power on the other hand is the product of the torque T and angular speed ω ($\omega = 2\pi \cdot f$), and thus is defined by $P_S = T \cdot \omega$ [23]. Hence the efficiency of a pump can be described by the following equation:

$$\eta = \frac{P_E}{P_S} = \frac{\dot{V} \cdot \Delta p}{T \cdot \omega} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The mechanical power input is only partially converted into the effectively usable power, while a large portion of the energy introduced via the shaft is dissipated due to power losses.

A.1.3. Chemical reactions

Chemical reactions can be seen as a rearrangement of molecular bonds and are often described by reaction equations, which are usually written as in the following example:

Meaning that ν_A parts of Substance A react with ν_B parts of Substance B forming ν_C parts of Substance C and ν_D parts of Substance D. A and B are consumed in the reaction and are

therefore called educts. C and D are formed during the reaction, hence they are called products. The ν_j are the stoichiometric numbers of the different substances participating in the reaction. In this work the convention that the stoichiometric numbers of educts are negative and the stoichiometric numbers of products are positive, is applied.

To describe the progress of chemical reactions, suitable key figures are the conversion X , the Selectivity S and the Yield Y . The conversion X_i describes the amount of a substance j that is converted during a reaction in relation to the initial amount of Substance j :

$$X_j(t) = \frac{n_j(t=0) - n_j(t)}{n_j(t=0)} = \frac{c_j(t=0) - c_j(t)}{c_j(t=0)}$$

or in case of a stationary, open system

$$X_j(t) = \frac{\dot{n}_{j,\text{in}}(t) - \dot{n}_{j,\text{out}}(t)}{\dot{n}_{j,\text{in}}(t)}$$
(A.2)

The selectivity $S_{j,k}$ on the other hand is the amount of substance j formed during the reaction in relation to the amount of substance k converted during the reaction:

$$S_{j,k}(t) = \frac{n_j(t) - n_j(t=0)}{n_k(t=0) - n_k(t)} \cdot \frac{|\nu_k|}{|\nu_j|} = \frac{c_j(t) - c_j(t=0)}{c_k(t=0) - c_k(t)} \cdot \frac{|\nu_k|}{|\nu_j|}$$

or in case of a stationary, open system

$$S_{j,k}(t) = \frac{\dot{n}_{j,\text{out}}(t) - \dot{n}_{j,\text{in}}(t)}{\dot{n}_{k,\text{in}}(t) - \dot{n}_{k,\text{out}}(t)} \cdot \frac{|\nu_k|}{|\nu_j|}$$
(A.3)

The yield $Y_{j,k}$ is the amount of substance j that is formed during the reaction relative to the amount of substance k at the beginning of the reaction:

$$Y_{j,k}(t) = \frac{n_j(t) - n_j(t=0)}{n_k(t=0)} \cdot \frac{|\nu_k|}{|\nu_j|} = \frac{c_j(t) - c_j(t=0)}{c_k(t=0)} \cdot \frac{|\nu_k|}{|\nu_j|}$$

or in case of a stationary, open system

$$Y_{j,k}(t) = \frac{\dot{n}_{j,\text{out}}(t) - \dot{n}_{j,\text{in}}(t)}{\dot{n}_{k,\text{in}}(t)} \cdot \frac{|\nu_k|}{|\nu_j|}$$
(A.4)

Conversion, yield and selectivity are connected via the following relationship:

$$Y_{j,k} = X_k \cdot S_{j,k}$$
(A.5)

A.1.4. Derivation of balance equations for chemical reactors

Fig. A.3.: Differential element surrounded by its environment with the concentration c

The balance for the amount of substance (AoS) in an differential element with the volume ΔV in which convection and reaction occur (diffusion is neglected) can be described by the following equation:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \left(\sum_{\text{in}} \dot{n}|_j - \sum_{\text{out}} \dot{n}|_{j+\Delta j} \right) + B \cdot \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{rr} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

The first term in Eq. (A.6) describes the accumulation of the AoS in the differential element. The second term describes the transport through the surface of the volume by convection and the third term describes the conversion by chemical reactions with B being the reference value, $\underline{\nu}$ a matrix containing the stoichiometric numbers of all N components for all R reactions. The mole flow that enters the element can be described by:

$$\dot{n}|_j = \Delta A_{k,l} \cdot u_j(j) \cdot c_{\text{env}} = \Delta A_{k,l} \cdot (u_j \cdot \underline{c})|_j \quad (\text{A.7})$$

While the mole flow that exits the differential element is defined by:

$$\dot{n}|_{j+\Delta j} = \Delta A_{k,l} \cdot u_j(j + \Delta j) \cdot c_{\text{de}} = A_{k,l} \cdot (u_j \cdot \underline{c})|_{j+\Delta j} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

With c_{de} being the concentration inside of the differential element. The accumulated AoS in the differential element can be substituted by:

$$dn = dc \cdot \Delta V = dc \cdot \Delta x \cdot \Delta y \cdot \Delta z \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Insertion of Eq.(A.7 - A.9) into Eq. (A.6) results in:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d\underline{c} \cdot \Delta x \cdot \Delta y \cdot \Delta z}{dt} = & \Delta y \cdot \Delta z \cdot ((u_x \cdot \underline{c})|_x - (u_x \cdot \underline{c})|_{x+\Delta x}) \\
 & + \Delta x \cdot \Delta z \cdot ((u_y \cdot \underline{c})|_y - (u_y \cdot \underline{c})|_{y+\Delta y}) \\
 & + \Delta x \cdot \Delta y \cdot ((u_z \cdot \underline{c})|_z - (u_z \cdot \underline{c})|_{z+\Delta z}) \\
 & + \Delta V \cdot \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{rr}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A.10}$$

By dividing Eq. (A.10) by Δx , Δy and Δz and formulation of the respective limes ($\lim \Delta x \rightarrow 0$), ($\lim \Delta y \rightarrow 0$) and ($\lim \Delta z \rightarrow 0$), Eq. (A.10) can be applied to a finite volume:

$$\frac{\delta \underline{c}}{\delta t} = \left(-\frac{\delta(u_x \cdot \underline{c})}{\delta x} - \frac{\delta(u_y \cdot \underline{c})}{\delta y} - \frac{\delta(u_z \cdot \underline{c})}{\delta z} \right) + \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{rr} \tag{A.11}$$

With further simplification leading to:

$$\frac{\delta \underline{c}}{\delta t} = -\vec{\nabla}(\vec{u} \cdot \underline{c}) + \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{rr} \tag{A.12}$$

A.1.5. Conservation laws

If no chemical reaction occurs, the amount of substance in an open system is subject to the conservation of mass and thus can be described by the following system of partial differential equations (PDE), which is derived in section A.1.4:

$$\frac{\delta \underline{c}}{\delta t} = -\vec{\nabla}(\vec{u} \cdot \underline{c}) \tag{A.13}$$

The solution of the PDEs at the outlet of the System for a input pulse (a dirac delta function) and given flow rate and volume is the exit age distribution $E(t)$ of the balanced system (e.g. a vessel, reactor, tube, etc.). $E(t)$ also known as the residence time distribution (RTD) is the temporal distribution of the probability that a particle that entered the system with the input pulse leaves the system at a time t and thus can be a useful tool to describe the mixing on a macroscopic scale inside the system. [1, 18]

To determine the RTD, the concentration of a tracer substance at the in- and outlet of the examined system must be continuously recorded. First the system is purged, so that there are no residues of the tracer. Then the input is altered by injecting a certain amount of a tracer substance into the system, ideally in form of an impulse or a rectangular step. If the input is in form of an impulse, the recorded and normalized concentration at the output is the exit age distribution $E(t)$, if the input represents a rectangular step the response at the output is called $F(t)$. The following relationship exists between $E(t)$ and $F(t)$:

$$F(t) = \int_0^t E(\tau) d\tau \tag{A.14}$$

Neither an impulse nor a rectangular step is easy to accomplish experimentally. However the response for an arbitrary input $c_{in}(t)$ can be computed by convolving the input with $E(t)$ [18, 24]:

$$c_{out}(t) = c_{in}(t) * E(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} c_{in}(\tau)E(t - \tau)d\tau \quad (A.15)$$

To obtain $E(t)$ from the relationship described in eq. A.15 a deconvolution must be performed (for further reading cf. Sec. A.7).

Another term in the context of the RTD is the space time $\bar{\tau}$:

$$\bar{\tau} = \frac{V}{\dot{V}} \quad (A.16)$$

The space time $\bar{\tau}$ is the mean time, a fluid element resides inside the system, hence it is the median of the RTD. The reciprocal of $\bar{\tau}$ is called space velocity and describes how many reactor volumes are fed through the system per unit of time [18].

In reactive systems with N Components and R reactions, the material balance (cf. eq. A.13) must be extended by a source/sink term. The concentration-related material balance of a reactive system can be described by the following system of partial differential equation, which is derived in section A.1.4:

$$\frac{\delta \underline{c}}{\delta t} = -\vec{\nabla}(\vec{u} \cdot \underline{c}) + \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{rr} \quad (A.17)$$

The first term in Eq. (A.17) describes the accumulation in the reactor volume, the second term the convection and the third term the reactions that occur in the reactor. The Matrix $\underline{\nu}$ being a $N \times R$ matrix is containing the stoichiometric numbers of the N Components for all R Reactions and \underline{rr} being a $R \times 1$ vector containing the reaction rates for all R Reactions. Note, that in this work the reaction rate is always referred to the systems volume, so that the reference value, with which the reaction rate is multiplied, is always canceled out in the concentration-based balance. However in a more general case, one must consider the reference value of the reaction rate.

A.1.6. Ideal reactor models

In terms of mixing there are two types of ideal reactor models. The first one being the ideal plug flow reactor (PFR) and the second one the ideal CSTR. For the ideal PFR (flow along the z -axis) following assumptions can be made:

- No parabolic flow profile $\frac{\delta u}{\delta x} = \frac{\delta u}{\delta y} = 0$
- No radial concentration gradient $\frac{\delta c}{\delta x} = \frac{\delta c}{\delta y} = 0$
- No backmixing

With those assumptions, Eq. (A.17) can be simplified:

$$\frac{\delta \underline{c}}{\delta t} = -\frac{\delta(u \cdot \underline{c})}{\delta z} + \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{r} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

The ideal CSTR on the other hand behaves like a differential element (cf. Subsec. A.1.4), thus all spatial concentration gradients inside the vessel equal zero. The substance balance of a CSTR can be described by the following system of ODEs:

$$\frac{dn_{\text{out}}}{dt} = (\dot{n}_{\text{in}} - \dot{n}_{\text{out}}) + V_R \cdot \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{r} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

and concentration-based:

$$\frac{dc_{\text{out}}}{dt} = \frac{\dot{V}}{V_R} \cdot (c_{\text{in}} - c_{\text{out}}) + \underline{\nu} \cdot \underline{r} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

A.2. Further information on the experimental set up

A.2.1. List of the equipment used

Category	Designation in Flowsheet	Manufacturer (Supplier)	Designation by supplier	Comments
Control units	Frequency converter	Toshiba		
	Photo sensor control unit	Workshops of the RPTU		
Data acquisition	Valve control unit	Workshops of the RPTU		
	Data logger	Ahlborn		
Flow sensor	FI 1	Kobold	ALMEMO 2890-9	with Option "Q4"
	-	Imaging solutions GmbH	DUK-12G4HC34PB	Range: 0.08 - 12 L.min ⁻¹
High speed camera	-	Workshops of the RPTU	Os 8 S3	Housing, wiring, control unit
	PS 1, PS 2	Cree	C503B	LED, amber red
Photo sensor	-	Siemens	BPY62	Phototransistor
	PR 2	Ahlborn	FDAD3301NR	Range: ± 1 bar
Pressure sensor	PR 5	Ahlborn	FDA602L5R	Range: 0 - 10 bar
	P 1	K-Engineering	HMI 100	
RMP	-	(hbholzmaus)	10/8 mm Acrylglas Rohr klar	PMMA 10x8 mm
	-	Sang-A (Drumm GmbH)	PUN 10x8 LE KLAR	PUN 10x8 mm
Tubes	-	Sang-A (Drumm GmbH)	PUN 8x5 LE KLAR	PUN 8x5 mm
	-	Sang-A (Drumm GmbH)	different Variations	IQS-Connector
Tube fittings	V1, V6 - V8	Festo (Drumm GmbH)	C1866022	Solenoid valve
	V2	Sang-A (Drumm GmbH)	IQSKH 100	Ball valve
Valves	V3 - V4			Plug valve
	V5	Sang-A (Drumm GmbH)	IQSKH 80	Ball valve
Voltage sensor	V9	(Drumm GmbH)	NADEL 12 HR ES	Needle valve
	ER 3, ER 4	Ahlborn	ZA9602-FS	Range: ± 26 V

A.2.2. Drawing of the RMP and geometrical properties

Fig. A.4.: Drawing of the RMP with its geometrical parameters

Region	Name	Symbole	Value	Aquisition
Impeller channel	Inner radius of impeller	$r_{i,imp}$	32.5 mm	datasheet
	Outer radius of impeller	$r_{o,imp}$	40.0 mm	datasheet
	Curvature radius of impeller surface	$r_{cur,imp}$	14.443 mm	calculated
	Thickness of impeller	t_{imp}	5.05 mm	datasheet
	Thickness of impeller tip	$t_{tip,imp}$	0.8 mm	measured
	Thickness of impeller blade	$t_{bl,imp}$	0.8 mm	measured
	Number of blades	B	60	datasheet
Side channel	Inner radius of side channel	$r_{i,sc}$	32.5 mm	datasheet
	Outer radius of side channel	$r_{o,sc}$	42.5 mm	datasheet
	Curvature radius of side channel corners	$r_{cur,sc}$	3.25 mm	datasheet
	Thickness of side channel	t_{sc}	3.45 mm	datasheet
	Angle of side channel	φ_{sc}	315	datasheet
Breaker channel	Outer radius of breaker channel	$r_{o,bc}$	40.15 mm	datasheet
	Thickness of breaker channel	t_{bc}	5.3 mm	datasheet
	Angle of breaker channel	φ_{bc}	45	datasheet

A.2.3. Assembly and calibration of the photosensors

A schematic drawing of the photosensors used is shown in the following figure:

Fig. A.5.: Schematic assembly of the photosensor. The orange line represents the light emitted by the LED. The drawing also illustrates the absorption of the light that occurs when radiation is transmitted through conduit and tracer solution.

The sensors sensitivity and the intensity of the light emitted by the LED were regulated by a control unit which is shown in the following picture.

Fig. A.6.: Control unit of the photosensor. The unit consists of two knobs. One for setting the sensitivity of the phototransistor ("Empfindlichkeit") and one for setting the intensity of the light emitted by the LED ("Sender").

To find an adequate combination of sensitivity and intensity, preliminary tests were conducted. Different settings were tested. On the one hand the test rig was filled with water and on the other hand with tracer solution. The results are shown in the following figure.

Fig. A.7.: Voltage measured depending on the selected sensitivity of the photosensor for different LED settings and tracer concentrations A) no tracer, B) tracer concentration of 0.05 g L^{-1} . The curves shown refer to the photosensor at the inlet of the pump.

In Fig. A.7 it can be seen that the measured voltage decreases with increasing sensitivity. With increasing intensity of the emitted light, the gradient increases. If there is no tracer in the conduit, fluctuations at higher sensitivities can be observed, increasing at low intensities. The sensitivity of the sensor must therefore be selected so high that stable measurements are possible even at low tracer concentrations. At the same time, it must be taken into account that the voltage range usable for the measurement decreases with increasing sensitivity. Analogous to the previous consideration, the brightness of the LED must also be adjusted accordingly. The following combination was determined for later experiments: ("Sender"=80, "Empfindlichkeit"=50). After the selected parameters were set on the LED control unit, the calibration of the photosensors could be carried out. For this purpose, a stock solution was prepared with a tracer concentration of 5 g L^{-1} , from which calibration solutions were then prepared. Before the test rig could be filled with the calibration solution, it was rinsed with water for at least 5 minutes at low driving frequencies (5-10 Hz). T1 was then filled with 2 L of the calibration solution and the pump was operated at low driving frequencies. This was done until T1 was completely drained and the calibration solution displaced the water in the test rig.

The obtained calibration curves for the sensors at the in- and outlet of the RMP are shown in the following figure:

Fig. A.8.: Calibration of the photosensor. A) Sensor at the inlet of the pump and B) Sensor at the outlet of the pump. The figure also contains the calibration curve (line).

Since there is no recognizable mathematical relationship between the concentration and the voltage, an interpolation is performed between the individual calibration points to obtain the calibration curve. The interpolation was carried out using cubic, hermit Splines (PCHIPInterpolation.jl Package in Julia).

A.3. Alternative approaches to determine the tracer concentration

During the calibration of the photosensors an alternative approach to determine the concentration inside the RMP and the in- and outlet region was tested using a method based on image processing. For this method, images were taken with the high speed camera at different tracer concentrations. Upstream of the inlet of the pump a transparent pipe segment was placed. Pictures of the inside of this segment were taken using an industrial camera in combination with telecentric optics. In contrast to the high speed camera the industrial camera has a color sensor.

To obtain a calibration function for the concentration inside the RMP the grey value of the images was evaluated at the in- and outlet region inside the pump for the different calibration concentrations. An example image containing the evaluated regions is shown below.

Fig. A.9.: Picture of the pump taken with the high speed cam. The picture also contains the region (indicated by red and green box), at the in- and outlet of the pump in which the grey value was analyzed.

The following figure contains the grey value of the two regions shown in Fig. A.9 for the different calibration points.

Fig. A.10.: Grey value for different tracer concentrations. A) at the inlet of the RMP and B) at the outlet

For the calibration of the image sensors upstream of the pump the respective RGB-values of the images taken during the calibration with the industrial camera were analyzed. Four pictures taken with the camera are shown exemplary in the following figure:

Fig. A.11.: Images of the pipe segment taken at different tracer concentrations. A) 0 g L^{-1} , B) 0.15 g L^{-1} , C) 0.35 g L^{-1} and D) 0.05 g L^{-1} . The red box indicates the region in which the RGB-values were analyzed.

The following figure contains the RGB-values for different tracer concentrations:

Fig. A.12.: RGB values at different tracer concentrations obtained from images taken of the pipe segment.

Fig. A.10 and A.12 indicate, that image processing methods could be used in the future for concentration measurements. However it must be taken into account, that the calibration is very sensitive to environmental factors such as ambient light.

For the high speed camera, brighter and more homogeneous illumination would also have to be achieved. The proposed method could make it possible to resolve the concentration not only temporally but also spatially.

A.4. Error estimation

A.4.1. Pump characteristic curves

The main error in measuring the pump characteristic curves occurs because there is a certain distance between the pressure sensors and the inlet of the pump. The same applies to the pump outlet. Friction losses occur within this distance. The friction losses are dependent on the respective flow rate, the length, diameter and the friction factor ζ of the conduit. The pressure loss due to pipe friction can be described by the following equation [25]:

$$\Delta p_{\text{friction}} = \zeta_{\text{conduit}} \cdot \frac{l_{\text{conduit}}}{2 \cdot r_{\text{conduit}}} \cdot \frac{\rho}{2} \cdot u^2 \quad (\text{A.21})$$

ζ_{friction} can be defined implicit by the following equation [25]:

$$0 = -2 \cdot \log \left[\frac{2.51}{\text{Re} \cdot \sqrt{\zeta_{\text{conduit}}}} + \frac{\epsilon_{\text{conduit}}}{7.42 \cdot r_{\text{conduit}}} \right] - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\zeta_{\text{conduit}}}} \quad (\text{A.22})$$

With $\epsilon_{\text{conduit}}$ being the conduits roughness (a material constant). For the pipes made of PMMA, a value of 0.0015 mm is assumed for $\epsilon_{\text{conduit}}$ [25]. Re is the Reynolds number and can be determined by the following equation [25]:

$$\text{Re} = \frac{u \cdot \rho \cdot 2 \cdot r_{\text{conduit}}}{\mu} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

With μ being the dynamic viscosity of the fluid. In this work, water at 20° C is assumed, which means that the value of μ is $1001.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Pa s [25]. The pressure loss due to the height difference h of the two sensors can be determined by the following formula:

$$\Delta p_{\text{height}} = \rho \cdot g \cdot h \quad (\text{A.24})$$

The sum of both $\Delta p_{\text{friction}}$ and Δp_{height} describe the pressure difference that is not achieved by the pump but by the described phenomena.

A.5. Calculation of the trust region for the ζ -parameters

To estimate the trust region of the model used to calculate the pump curves a method described in [13] is used. For this purpose the jacobian J of the function is needed. The single elements of the jacobian matrix are defined as:

$$J_{j,k} = \left[\frac{\delta \Delta p(f_{\text{imp,exp},j}, \dot{V}_{\text{exp},j}, \zeta)}{\delta \zeta_k} \right]_{\zeta = \zeta_{\text{opt}}} \quad (\text{A.25})$$

First the derivative of the model for the different parameters is approximated by:

$$J_{j,k} \approx \frac{\Delta p(f_{\text{imp,exp},j}, \dot{V}_{\text{exp},j}, \zeta_{\text{opt}}) - \Delta p(f_{\text{imp,exp},j}, \dot{V}_{\text{exp},j}, \zeta_{k,\text{opt,var}})}{\Delta \zeta_{k,\text{var}}} \quad (\text{A.26})$$

With $\zeta_{k,\text{var}}$ being one of the obtained ζ_{opt} -parameters varied by a certain value e.g. 1 %, while the other two are left on their optimum value. The $(1-\alpha)$ trust region of the parameter is defined by:

$$\zeta_{k,\text{opt}} \pm se(\zeta_k) \cdot t(n_j - n_k, \frac{\alpha}{2}) \quad (\text{A.27})$$

With $se(\zeta_k)$ being the standard error and $t(n_j - n_k, \frac{\alpha}{2})$ the students distribution. n_j represent the number of data points and n_k the number of parameters. The standard error can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$se(\zeta_k) = \sqrt{\frac{SSE}{n_j - n_k} (J'J)_{kk}^{-1}} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

SSE i.e. sum of squared errors is the value of the objective function (cf. Eq. (3.1)) at ζ_{opt} .

A.6. Number of circulations

To calculate the number of circulations C , first the speed of the circulation u_{circ} is calculated by dividing Eq. (2.3) with $(A_{\text{circ, cen}} \cdot \rho)$. In combination with the distance l_{circ} , a fluid element that travels on the circular path described in (cf. Fig. 2.3), the time required for circulation can be calculated:

$$t_{\text{circ}} = \frac{l_{\text{circ}}}{u_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{\pi(r_{\text{circ},2} - r_{\text{circ},1})}{u_{\text{circ}}} \quad (\text{A.29})$$

While circulating, the fluid element also travels in the axial direction leading to the spiral shaped trajectory described in Subsec. 2.1.2. The distance l_{ax} , the fluid element travels in the axial direction while performing a full rotation, thus can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$l_{\text{ax}} = \frac{t_{\text{circ}}}{2} \cdot (u_{\text{sc}} + u_{\text{imp}}) = \frac{t_{\text{circ}}}{2} \cdot (u_{\text{sc}}^* + \omega_{\text{imp}} \cdot r_{\text{imp, cen}}) \quad (\text{A.30})$$

The total length l_{RMP} (distance between in- and outlet) of the RMP is defined by:

$$l_{\text{RMP}} = 2\pi \cdot r_{\text{RMP, cen}} \cdot \frac{\varphi_{\text{sc}}}{360} = 2\pi \cdot \frac{A_{\text{imp}} \cdot r_{\text{imp, cen}} + A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*}{A_{\text{imp}} + A_{\text{sc}}^*} \cdot \frac{\varphi_{\text{sc}}}{360} \quad (\text{A.31})$$

The ratio of l_{RMP} and l_{ax} describes the number of whole circulations a fluid element can perform while passing through the RMP.

$$C = \frac{l_{\text{RMP}}}{l_{\text{ax}}} \quad (\text{A.32})$$

Since Eq. (A.32) will not always compute integers, the result was rounded to the next lower integer.

A.7. Convolution

With the RTD $E(t)$ being the impulse response of an open system and the assumption that the balanced system is linear and time-invariant, the response, i.e. the concentration at the outlet of the system $c_{\text{out}}(t)$ for an arbitrary input concentration $c_{\text{in}}(t)$ can be calculated by convolving the input with the RTD [18, 24]:

$$c_{\text{out}}(t) = c_{\text{in}}(t) * E(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} c_{\text{in}}(t) \cdot E(t - \tau) d\tau \quad (\text{A.33})$$

To obtain the RTD $E(t)$ from the correlation proposed in Eq. (A.33) a deconvolution must be performed. A common way to compute a deconvolution utilizes the fact that the convolution in the time domain becomes a multiplication in the frequency domain [26]. Hence, the following equation applies:

$$C_{\text{out}}(\omega) = C_{\text{in}}(\omega) \cdot E(\omega) = \text{DFFT}(c_{\text{in}}(t) * E(t)) \quad (\text{A.34})$$

With $C_{\text{out}}(\omega)$, $C_{\text{in}}(\omega)$ and $E(\omega)$ being the fourier transform of $c_{\text{out}}(t)$, $c_{\text{in}}(t)$ and $E(t)$ respectively. $E(t)$ can then be calculated by following equation:

$$E_{\text{out}}(t) = \text{iDFFT} \left(\frac{C_{\text{out}}(\omega)}{C_{\text{in}}(\omega)} \right) \quad (\text{A.35})$$

However raw deconvolution of experimental data is very sensitive to noise and thus filtering is needed. In this work, a filtering method proposed in [10] is used, which adds a digital filter using a smoothing factor γ to the deconvolution term (cf. Eq. (3.2)). The outcome of the deconvolution for different smoothing factors is shown in the following figure:

Fig. A.13.: Influence of the smoothing factor γ on the deconvolution.

Fig. A.13 illustrates, that the residence time distribution $E(t)$ obtained via deconvolution of $c_{\text{out}}(t)$ with $c_{\text{in}}(t)$ depends very strongly on the chosen smoothing factor γ . Therefore γ should be chosen in such a way that the noise is filtered out while important properties of $E(t)$ are preserved.

To estimate γ , a method based on the additive property of the statistical moments derived in [18] is proposed in [10]. For this method, the zeroth to second order moment of the tracer input and output response is computed according to the following equation.:

$$\mu_{n,\text{input}} = \int_0^{t_\infty} t^n \cdot c_{\text{in,exp}}(t) dt \quad (\text{A.36})$$

The n -th moment of the tracer output is calculated by replacing $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$ with $c_{\text{out,exp}}(t)$, respectively. The n -th moment of the tracer impulse response can be computed by replacing $c_{\text{in,exp}}(t)$

with $E(t)$ in Eq. A.36, whereas $E(t)$ is the inverse fourier transform of $E(\omega)$ calculated from Eq. 3.2. Mills, Levenspiel et al. [10, 18] propose that the following equation applies:

$$\mu_{n,E} = \Delta\mu_{n,\text{exp}} = \mu_{n,\text{out}} - \mu_{n,\text{in}} \quad (\text{A.37})$$

Which ultimately leads to the following optimization problem:

$$\min_{\underline{\gamma}} \left\| \left(\mu_{\text{E}} - \frac{\Delta\mu_{\text{exp}}}{2} \right) \right\|_2^2 \quad (\text{A.38})$$

This optimization problem was solved by using the package `optim.jl` [27] in Julia.

A.8. Flow fractions inside the RMP

The flow fractions inside the RMP can be derived from the fluid dynamic model (cf. Sec. 2.2):

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{\frac{\omega_{\text{imp}}}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{LR}}}{2}}{A_{\text{circ, cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2 \right) \cdot \left(\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \left(\frac{u_{\text{sc}}}{r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*} \right)^2 \right)}} \quad (\text{A.39})$$

and

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{\frac{A_{\text{sc}}^*}{2} \cdot u_{\text{s}}^* c}{A_{\text{circ, cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2 \right) \cdot \left(\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \left(\frac{u_{\text{sc}}}{r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*} \right)^2 \right)}} \quad (\text{A.40})$$

With $u_{\text{sc}}^* = \omega_{\text{sc}} \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*$ Eq. (A.39) and (A.40) can be simplified to:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ, cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2 \right)}} \cdot \frac{\omega_{\text{imp}}}{\sqrt{\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \omega_{\text{sc}}^2}} \quad (\text{A.41})$$

and

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*}{2 \cdot A_{\text{circ, cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2 \right)}} \cdot \frac{\omega_{\text{sc}}}{\sqrt{\omega_{\text{imp}}^2 - \omega_{\text{sc}}^2}} \quad (\text{A.42})$$

A new variable $\xi_{j,k}$ is now introduced describing the ratio of angular speeds:

$$\xi_{j,k} = \frac{\omega_j}{\omega_k} \quad (\text{A.43})$$

Using this definition Eq. (A.41) and (A.42) can be further simplified:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ,cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \xi_{\text{sc,imp}}^2}} \quad (\text{A.44})$$

and

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} = \frac{A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc,cen}}^*}{2 \cdot A_{\text{circ,cen}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)}} \cdot \frac{\xi_{\text{sc,imp}}}{\sqrt{1 - \xi_{\text{sc,imp}}^2}} \quad (\text{A.45})$$

The left term of the right hand side of Eq. (A.44) and (A.45) only depends on geometric parameters, while the right term is depending on the operating point of the pump. If distinct crossmixing is desired, the following equations must apply:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.46})$$

and

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{circ}}} \leq 1 \quad (\text{A.47})$$

Eq. (A.44) can be used to calculate the highest $\xi_{\text{sc,imp}}$ for which Eq. (A.46) is satisfied:

$$\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} \leq \sqrt{\frac{4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)} - V_{\text{imp}}}{4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)}}} \quad (\text{A.48})$$

and respectively derived from Eq. (A.45) and (A.47):

$$\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} \leq \frac{4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)}}{\sqrt{(A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc,cen}}^*)^2 - \left(4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},1}^2)}\right)^2}} \quad (\text{A.49})$$

Another term in this context of mixing performance is the ratio of the recycled and the conveyed flow rate, i.e. the holdup:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}} + \dot{V}_{\text{bc}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^* - \dot{V}_{\text{bc}}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*} \cdot \frac{1 + \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{bc}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}}{1 - \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{bc}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}} \quad (\text{A.50})$$

$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{sc}}^*}$ can be derived by multiplying Eq. (A.44) with the reciprocal of Eq. (A.45), which simplifies Eq. (A.46):

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{2\pi \cdot A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \cdot \xi_{\text{sc, imp}}} \cdot \frac{1 + \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{bc}}}{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}}}{1 - \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{bc}}}{V_{\text{sc}}^*}} \quad (\text{A.51})$$

With the definitions for \dot{V}_{imp} , \dot{V}_{sc} and \dot{V}_{bc} Eq. (A.47) becomes:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{2\pi \cdot A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \cdot \xi_{\text{sc, imp}}} \cdot \frac{1 + \frac{2\pi \cdot u_{\text{bc}} \cdot A_{\text{bc}}}{V_{\text{imp}} \cdot \omega_{\text{imp}}}}{1 - \frac{u_{\text{bc}} \cdot A_{\text{bc}}}{A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \cdot \omega_{\text{sc}}}} \quad (\text{A.52})$$

And by further simplifying:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{imp}} \cdot \omega_{\text{imp}} + 2\pi \cdot u_{\text{bc}} \cdot A_{\text{bc}}}{A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \cdot \omega_{\text{sc}} - u_{\text{bc}} \cdot A_{\text{bc}}} \quad (\text{A.53})$$

Now analogous to previous considerations ($u_{\text{bc}} = r_{\text{bc, cen}} \cdot \omega_{\text{bc}}$ and $\xi_{\text{bc, imp}} = \frac{\omega_{\text{bc}}}{\omega_{\text{imp}}}$):

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{imp}} + V_{\text{bc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{bc, imp}}}{A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* \cdot \xi_{\text{sc, imp}} - A_{\text{bc}} \cdot r_{\text{bc, cen}} \cdot \xi_{\text{bc, imp}}} \quad (\text{A.54})$$

With A_{sc}^* being $A_{\text{sc}} + A_{\text{bc}}$ and $r_{\text{sc, cen}}^* = \frac{A_{\text{sc}} \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}} + A_{\text{bc}} \cdot r_{\text{bc, cen}}}{A_{\text{sc}}^*}$ following equation derives from Eq. (A.50):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{imp}} + V_{\text{bc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{bc, imp}}}{A_{\text{sc}} \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}} \cdot \xi_{\text{sc, imp}} - A_{\text{bc}} \cdot r_{\text{bc, cen}} \cdot (\xi_{\text{bc, imp}} - \xi_{\text{bc, imp}})} \\ &= \frac{V_{\text{imp}} + V_{\text{bc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{bc, imp}}}{\frac{360}{\varphi_{\text{sc}}} \cdot V_{\text{sc}} \cdot \xi_{\text{sc, imp}} + V_{\text{bc}} \cdot (\xi_{\text{sc, imp}} - \xi_{\text{bc, imp}})} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.55})$$

Since $V_{\text{bc}} \ll V_{\text{sc}}$ and $V_{\text{bc}} \ll V_{\text{imp}}$, the following approximation can be made:

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} \approx \frac{\varphi_{\text{sc}}}{360} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{V_{\text{sc}}} \cdot \frac{1}{\xi_{\text{sc, imp}}} \quad (\text{A.56})$$

For a dominant backmixing, \dot{V}_{imp}^* should always be higher than \dot{V}_{in} :

$$\frac{\dot{V}_{\text{imp}}^*}{\dot{V}_{\text{in}}} \geq 1 \quad (\text{A.57})$$

and thus the following equation applies:

$$\xi_{\text{sc, imp}} \leq \frac{\varphi_{\text{sc}}}{360} \cdot \frac{V_{\text{imp}}}{V_{\text{sc}}} \quad (\text{A.58})$$

Eq. (A.48), (A.49) and (A.58), all describe the maximum $\xi_{\text{sc,imp}}$ -value for which Eq (A.46), (A.47) and (A.57) are satisfied respectively. However it is of interest to find a value for $\xi_{\text{sc,imp,max}}$, that satisfies all of the three equations. To find this ξ -value, the minimum of the three equations needs to be determined. For a better overview first the equations are simplified:

- Eq. (A.48): $\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} \leq \sqrt{\frac{a-b}{a}}$
- Eq. (A.49): $\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} \leq \frac{a}{\sqrt{c^2+a^2}}$
- Eq. (A.58): $\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} \leq \frac{b}{d}$

The ξ -value for which all equations are satisfied can be found by applying the following equation:

$$\xi_{\text{sc,imp}} \leq \min \left[\sqrt{\frac{a-b}{a}}; \frac{a}{\sqrt{c^2+a^2}}; \frac{b}{d} \right] \quad (\text{A.59})$$

With

- $a = 4\pi \cdot A_{\text{circ}} \cdot \zeta_{\text{circ}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(r_{\text{circ},2}^2 - r_{\text{circ},2}^* \right)}$
- $b = V_{\text{imp}}$
- $c = A_{\text{sc}}^* \cdot r_{\text{sc, cen}}^*$
- $d = V_{\text{sc}} \cdot \frac{360}{\varphi_{\text{sc}}}$

Which all depend on the geometry of the RMP.

A.9. Additional results from the simulative study

Tab. A.2.: Investigated operating points for the simulative study

Designation in Fig. A.14	$\dot{V}_{\text{in}}/\text{L min}^{-1}$	$\omega_{\text{imp}}/\text{s}^{-1}$	Δ_p/bar
A	0.17	29.4	2.44
B	1.47	29.4	2.17
C	2.04	29.4	2.07
D	5.61	29.4	1.07

Fig. A.14.: Pump characteristic curves (obtained from the fluid dynamic model) with different backmixing regions and the investigated operating points of the simulative study. Red zone: strongly backmixed, grey zone: backmixed, green zone: weakly backmixed, yellow zone: insufficiently backmixed. The division into the individual zones was done at the discretion of the author.

Fig. A.15.: Relative conversion for different operating points. The respective operating points are listed in Tab. A.2

Fig. A.16.: Relative selectivity for different operating points. The respective operating points are listed in Tab. A.2

Fig. A.17.: Relative yield for different operating points. The respective operating points are listed in Tab. A.2